

**D1.30 Annual Work Plan for
the sixth year
WP1 Coordination**

Responsible Partner: ANSES

Contributing partners: all partners

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	69 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Title OHEJP deliverable	D1.30 Annual Work Plan Year 6
WP and task	WP1 / Task 1.2
Leader	ANSES
Other contributors	All partners
Due month of the deliverable	M57
Actual submission month	M58
Type <i>R: Document, report DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services).</i>	PU <i>See updated Grant Agreement</i>
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	<p>OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>EFSA <input type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Other international stakeholder(s):</p> <p>Social Media:</p> <p>Other recipient(s):</p>

Table of content

1	Glossary	5
2	Coherence with annex 1.....	6
2.1	Expected impacts and objectives for month 61 to 69 (year 2023)	6
2.1.1	Coordination of activities	7
2.1.2	Finalisation of JRP/JIP/E&T.....	7
2.1.3	Dissemination	7
2.1.3.1	Dissemination workshop and Stakeholders Conference.....	8
2.1.3.2	Successful communication to optimise the dissemination actions	9
2.1.4	Legacy	10
2.2	Correspondence with the description of work – Annex 1.....	11
2.2.1	WP1	11
2.2.2	WP2	11
2.2.3	WP3	11
2.2.4	WP4	11
2.2.5	WP5	12
2.2.6	WP6	13
2.2.7	WP7	13
2.2.8	Timing of the different programmed activities and their components	14
2.2.9	Detailed work description	15
2.2.9.1	Annual work plan activities	15
2.2.9.1.1	WP1-Coordination and Management	15
2.2.9.1.2	WP2-Strategic Research Agenda	19
2.2.9.1.3	WP3-Management of Joint Research Projects.....	21
2.2.9.1.4	WP4–Management of Joint Integrative Projects	23
2.2.9.1.5	WP5-Science to policy translation.....	26
2.2.9.1.6	WP6-Training and Education.....	31
2.2.9.1.7	WP7-Sustainability	34
2.2.9.1.1	JIP06- SARS-CoV2 Research Integration and Preparednes-COVRIN	36
2.2.9.1.2	PhD03-R2-AMR2.1-HME-AMR	45
2.2.9.1.3	PhD04-R2-AMR2.1-KENTUCKY	46
2.2.9.1.4	PhD05-R2-AMR2/6.1/ET5-METAPRO	48
2.2.9.1.5	PhD07-R2-ET2.1-MACE.....	49
2.2.9.1.6	PhD08-R2-ET5.1/4.1/FBZSH3-DESIRE.....	51
2.2.9.1.7	PhD09-R2-FBZSH3/AMR2.1-UDOFRIC.....	53
2.2.9.1.8	PhD10-R2-FBZSH3/AMR2.1-WILBR	55
2.2.9.1.9	PhD11-R1-FBZ4/5- EnvDis	56

2.2.9.1.10	PhD13-R2-FBZ8/AMR2-VIMOGUT-AMR.....	59
2.2.9.1.11	PhD15-R2-FBZ5-TRACE.....	61
2.2.9.2	List of programmed activities.....	62
2.2.9.3	Annual Deliverables List.....	63
2.3	Participation in Annual Work Plan activities.....	65
2.3.1	P21-APHA.....	65
2.3.2	P31-WbVR.....	65
2.3.3	P41-SVA.....	66
2.4	Resources to be committed.....	67
2.4.1	Summary Effort Table.....	67
2.4.1.1	Overarching activities.....	67
2.4.1.2	Joint Integrative Project.....	69
2.4.2	Other major cost items (equipment, goods and services, travel & subsistence, meetings organisation).....	70

1 Glossary

ASM: Annual Scientific Meeting
AWP: Annual Work Plan
CaM: Communication workshop and Media training
CPD: Continuing Professional Development
CT: Coordination Team
E&T: Education and Training
ESAB: External Scientific Advisory Board
JIP: Joint Integrative Project
JRP: Joint Research Project
OH: One Health
OHEJP: One Health European Joint Programme
PMC: Programme Managers Committee
PMT: Project Management Team
POC: Programme Owners Committee
REA: Research Executive Agency
SPR: Summary Progress Report
SS: Summer School
SSB: Scientific Steering Board
ST: Support Team
STM: Short Term Mission
WS: Workshop

2 Coherence with annex 1

2.1 Expected impacts and objectives for month 61 to 69 (year 2023)

Annual Work Plan Y6, 2023		WP1	Comms team	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7
Coordination of activities		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
JRP, JIP & E&T	COVRIN (execute +) monitor					X			
	Finalisation of JRP, JIP, E&T				X	X		X	
Dissemination	Strategy	X	X				X		
	Inventory of outputs & outcomes						X		
	Identification of topics with PL				X	X	X	X	
	Brochures, case studies		X						
	Sharing with SH		X				X		
Legacy	Strategy	X		X					X
	SRIA						X		X
	Bilateral discussions with SH	X					X		X
Meetings organisation	Governance (PMT, SSB, PMC, POC; REA-SG)	X							
	SH Committee						X		
	SH Conference						X		
	Dissemination Workshops		X				X		
	Cross project dissemination meetings		X			X			
	Institutionalisation of One Health								X
	Legacy, see above	X					X		X
	Final meeting including Policy event and Press Conference	X							

In 2023, except for JIP06-COVRIN and some PhDs that started late in the lifespan of the OHEJP, all activities will have stopped on 31st December 2022, and only activities turned to finalisation of publications will be accepted in 2023. 2023 will be dedicated to finalisation of the OHEJP, around five main activities:

1. Coordination of OHEJP activities
2. Finalisation and external evaluation of the JRPs/JIPs by independent experts
3. Implementation of dissemination actions
4. Legacy of the One Health EJP
5. Dissemination meetings and final meeting

The 6th Year is specifically dedicated to ensure optimised dissemination efforts and a specific attention will be brought to legacy of outcomes produced during the five years of scientific implementation of the OHEJP. To that end a dissemination and impact strategy has been built up in course of the fifth year of the Action that will allow in several essential steps, to reach to maximum impact.

2.1.1 Coordination of activities

In the sixth year, the Coordination Team assisted by the Project Management Team will ensure that the annual workplan of the sixth year is correctly implemented. The CT will manage drafting of both the technical and financial reporting of the fifth year that will be submitted the Research Executive Agency.

2.1.2 Finalisation of JRP/JIP/E&T

The monitoring of the Joint Research Projects, which was the main task of WP3 and WP4 throughout the 5 years of the OHEJP, will be finished, since no research activities are planned for Y6 except JIP06-COVRIN which will end in March 2023. External independent experts will be appointed to undertake the final evaluation of all the JRP/JIPs that will have ended in December 2022.

In the sixth year, WP6 will continue to support and monitor the progress of PhDs. A final report of each PhD project consisting of either the final report of the PhD project (thesis paper) for already achieved PhD projects, or a final progress report for PhD projects still on-going in 2023 and/or 2024 will be drafted. WP6 will also report on the progress of the STMs that took place in the fifth year. WGs 3, 4 and 6 will meet regularly to discuss and align their approach to JRP/JIP/PhD follow-up and set deadlines.

2.1.3 Dissemination

The dissemination strategy was first discussed at the end of 2021, when the finalisation of the OHEJP started to be addressed. A specific working group on the dissemination strategy has been implemented among the PMT members since 2022 and will meet regularly in 2023 to review and revise the dissemination strategy according to the progress made. The dissemination strategy is closely linked to the legacy strategy, so that both aspects are addressed at the same time.

Dissemination activities will place particular attention to 1) facilitating the targeted dissemination of finalised, up-to-date scientific-based ready-to-use solutions to all interested parties, 2) supporting sustainability and resilience, and 3) advocating the One Health approach at the national, European and international level.

To reach these goals, WP5 will make use of its well established procedures for an efficient information flow to and from national, European and international stakeholders. It will ensure that outputs of research, innovation and integrative activities reach the most suitable national, EU and international stakeholders, focusing on closing the identified knowledge gaps. To identify said knowledge gaps, WP5 will be kept up to date with the EU key stakeholders' needs mainly by direct communication (the Stakeholders Committee meetings being the main tool), complemented indirectly via scanning of stakeholders' published documents. Identification of stakeholders' needs and relating them with OHEJP-

developed solutions will also support sustainability not just of individual solutions, but also of the project as a whole.

The OHEJP will ensure that output of research, innovation, and integrative activities reaches the various interested audiences using targeted dissemination mechanisms. These dissemination mechanisms are tailored to their audience, being them national, EU and international stakeholders, the scientific community, or the general population.

For example, the closure of stakeholders' knowledge gaps will be highlighted to the stakeholders in a series of occasions (the most important being the Stakeholders Committee meeting), and to all interested parties by a number of means including the One Health EJP Outcome Inventory, and the Data Management Plans.

Dissemination of outputs of PhD projects will be made through submission of their project deliverables, and publications following the appropriate dissemination procedure and scientific publication policy. The WP6 and Communications team will work together to identify new and improved ways of disseminating the successes of Work Package 6 and to increase the engagement when disseminating PhD project scientific research progress, and collaborative interactions by fostering a diverse and more engaging strategy through the OHEJP's communication channels both to internal and external target audiences. WP6 will also work with the communications team to convey the main outcomes of the STMs and testimonials from the awardees on the OHEJP website. The WP6 team will finally disseminate any outputs from any remaining activities (Summer School etc.).

In addition, WP3, WP4 and WP6 will support WP1, WP5, WP7 and the Communications Team to identify important results of the second call JRPs and JIPs and include these in the dissemination to national, EU and international stakeholders. In this way, the projects outcomes can be taken up and add to the scientific, societal and policy impact of the One Health EJP.

In particular new knowledge, tools and guidelines produced in the JIPs will harmonize and align the work between public health, animal health and food safety actors in the prevent-detect-response chain as implementation continues. This will contribute to increased food safety, sustainable animal production and improved public health.

To reach maximum impact it will be made sure that all publications from JRPs, JIPs and PhDs are uploaded on Zenodo and that they are available as Open Access.

OHEJP will continue to work so that even after the end of the funding period interested parties will have access to output and metadata produced in the OHEJP. Actions to support the sustainability and FAIRness of the produced data will include the curation and improvement of the One Health EJP Outcome Inventory (OHOI, which will be accessible after the end of the OHEJP) and of the Data Management Plans (DMPs, which will be available on Zenodo).

All deliverables of WP2 will have been delivered by the end of Y5. In Y6 WP2 will continue to monitor relevant scientific developments and provide input for the development of the strategy on sustainability developed in WP7. Furthermore, the web based database of relevant EU research projects and related initiatives will be updated. WP2 will help actively in all OHEJP dissemination plans regarding the main outputs of the project during all these years.

2.1.3.1 Dissemination workshop and Stakeholders Conference

Three important dissemination events targeted to stakeholders will take place in Y6: one Dissemination Workshop, one Stakeholder Conference and one Stakeholders Committee meeting. The Stakeholder Conference planned to take place from 19 to 21 June 2023 will represent a forum to advocate the One Health approach, to discuss on the science-policy interface for One Health (including opportunities and challenges to the uptake of outcomes by stakeholders), and to disseminate OHEJP solutions to European and international stakeholders, as well as to other interested parties (e.g. private sector).

Dissemination material consisting among others of dissemination brochures and Powerpoint presentations for each of the 24 JRPs and 6 JIPs are being prepared together by the Communications

Team and the Project Leaders and will be used for the dissemination workshop and the Stakeholder conference.

A great work about contribution of the One Health EJP to institutionalisation of One Health has been undertaken by WP7 and a restitution of the outcomes of this work will be carried out in parallel to the Stakeholder conference.

2.1.3.2 Successful communication to optimise the dissemination actions

The continued development and implementation of the Communication Strategy in Year 6 will ensure that the progress and outcomes of the OHEJP are effectively disseminated both internally and externally to the consortium and stakeholders. The key impacts in Year 6 are as follows:

- Regularly updating the OHEJP website with news, events and information will ensure that all recent information is available for those internal and external to the consortium. This will subsequently encourage collaboration and involvement in the OHEJP events and funding opportunities to aid sustainability. The links on the website will be moved from documents stored locally on the website to links that are on Zenodo – a sustainable open access repository.
- The completion of the website redevelopment and redesign will further showcase Consortium activities, outputs and impacts to ensure the legacy of OHEJP remains available.
- Further increasing the audience reach and engagement levels on the OHEJP social media channels will result in improved dissemination of OHEJP research and outcomes in this final year to ensure the legacy of the OHEJP. This will have significant positive impact on dissemination as we can reach individuals across the globe by tailoring messages and content to suit audiences.
- The success of OHEJP social media accounts, the traffic to the OHEJP website and the success of newsletters will continue to be monitored, which allows the Communication Team to monitor the success of the Communications Strategy and improve routes for dissemination.
- Sharing the Dissemination Information Pack, which includes documents such as the Communications Strategy, Dissemination Procedure and Publication Policy, will support the OHEJP consortium and aid in improving the dissemination of outcomes. Creating documents that are interactive and contain clear descriptive infographics, such as the Project Impact Brochures, are important in supporting consortium members share their work.
- Strengthening collaborations with all OHEJP Stakeholders will support better dissemination outcomes. For example, the Communications Team attends Stakeholder Committee meetings which encourages direct communications with stakeholders. The Communications Team directly engages with stakeholder’s social media accounts and collaborates with WP5 to share key information and use the information from the WP5 Scanning Documents to keep up to date with stakeholder activities.
- The internal and external newsletters will also benefit the internal and external communication from the OHEJP and ensure that all stakeholders are aware of our progress and achievements on a regular basis.
- The Annual Report and Final Reports for Stakeholder Number 5 will be published in Year 6 and will showcase all the OHEJP achievements from Years 5 and 6. This document will be disseminated to stakeholders and both those internal and external to the OHEJP. This will help promote the OHEJP and our research.
- Effective communication of OHEJP progress, news events, funding opportunities and Education and Training events will create a European One Health community of scientists who are experts in the one Health Field. The use of our social media platforms to increase our followers and

engagements will also contribute to developing this community of scientists, stakeholders, and public that have been interested in implementation of the One Health concept.

- The Communications Team will work with all the OHEJP Work Packages to ensure that our research outcomes and activities are effectively communicated with policy makers across the EU. This will continue to be a multifaceted approach and will require an internal network, including the CCPs, within the consortium to ensure that the impact of our work is resulting in translation of science to policy.
- Continued work to strengthen the visibility of the OHEJP brand and disseminate outcomes will focus on sustainability and legacy of the OHEJP outcomes beyond the end of the OHEJP.

2.1.4 Legacy

WP1 WP2 and WP7 will pursue the effort initiated since September 2021 to foster an impact-oriented approach of the governance meetings and make them effective ways to present outcomes and to demonstrate the impact of the One Health EJP on national and international stakeholders' activities.

A dedicated deliverable is being finalised ([D7.1](#) Analysis of outcomes and uptake of EJP's outputs by stakeholders) that will allow at a glance to showcase each of the main outcomes of each JRP/JIP. These dissemination and legacy materials will be used to undertake in 2023 bilateral discussions with key targeted stakeholders, at national, EU and international levels, in order to concretely discuss possibilities of uptake of the OHEJP main outcomes. The outcomes of these bilateral discussions will be addressed during the final meeting where a policy event as well as a press conference will be organised. The objective of such policy event is to publicly concretise agreements made during the bilateral discussions that can be under the form of:

- The use by stakeholders of data/methods/protocols/ produced by the OHEJP for RA purpose
- The mobilisation by stakeholders of OHEJP's scientists/JRP-JIP consortias/Med-Vet-Net Association members to respond to call of services as it is already the case regarding the IPA programme of EFSA, where the Med-Vet-Net Association will provide expertise taken over from the OHEJP activities, to train IPA countries to the use of the OH approach in their RA works.

WP2 and WP7 will provide the expertise to highlight the main strategic interactions that have been made with other projects/initiatives that assure the maintenance of OHEJP legacy.

The results from the OHEJP exercise SimEx undertaken by WP4 will be discussed with stakeholders to find out if the format can be further exploited and how the experiences can be taken forward.

WP5 will continue to work so that even after the end of the OHEJP that stakeholders have access to output and metadata produced in the OHEJP, by curating the One Health EJP Outcome Inventory (OHOI) and, in collaboration with WP4, the Data Management Plans (DMP). These tools, in parallel with forms of targeted dissemination, make OHEJP data available for the use of national, European and international risk assessment and risk management activities.

The Med-Vet-Net association will take over management and maintenance of the OHEJP website where all deliverables and publications will be kept publicly available.

The main objective of WP7 is to provide a strategy for the sustainability of the principal outcomes of the One Health EJP. The expected application of this strategy will result in important and sustained impacts, including i.) a network of laboratories and research centres with reference tasks in the domains of the One Health EJP, ii.) an improved "Prevent-Detect-Respond" approach throughout Europe, iii.) harmonized laboratory methods and protocols, shared databases and biological collections, iv.) interaction with European and national stakeholders, v.) platforms for the continuation of scientific activities. All these aspects will be taken over by the Med-Vet-Net Association which objective is to welcome part, most, if not all Beneficiaries of the OHEJP to continue implementing these sustained impacts.

2.2 Correspondence with the description of work – Annex 1

The following actions are foreseen in the sixth year:

2.2.1 WP1

WP1 work will be dedicated to supervision of the overall activities undertaken within the OHEJP and the reporting activities, namely Periodic Report of the fifth year, Summary Progress Report of the sixth year and the Final Report.

Financial follow-up of activities will be provided to ensure a good budgetary trajectory for the last year of the project allowing to have spent up to the maximum grant amount at the end of the OHEJP. The ST will also prepare the Final Report of the project.

Organisation support for the periodic meetings of the governance bodies as well as the Final project meeting will be provided.

The Communications Team will create Project Impact Brochures for all OHEJP JIPs and JRPs and Case Studies for all PhD projects during Year 6, which will highlight the key outcomes of each project. The Communications Team will collaborate with the Med-Vet-Net Association in Year 6 to ensure that management of the website will be transferred to their organisation once the One Health EJP ends, for the website sustainability to continue beyond the completion of OHEJP that will provide legacy for OHEJP research outcomes in the longer term.

2.2.2 WP2

All deliverables of WP2 will have been delivered by the end of Y5. In Y6 WP2 will continue to monitor relevant scientific developments and provide input for the strategy on sustainability developed in WP7. Furthermore, the web based database of relevant EU research projects and related initiatives will be updated. WP2 will help actively in all OHEJP dissemination plans regarding the main outputs of the project during all these years. It can help with its expertise to highlight the main strategic interactions that have been made with other projects/initiatives that assure the maintenance of OHEJP legacy.

2.2.3 WP3

All scientific activities related to the Joint Research Projects will have come to an end in Y6. However, Project Leaders still have to draft publications or reports, such as the final report and their contribution to the Periodic Report of Y5. WP3 will monitor this reporting.

The main activity of WP3 will be the dissemination of the project outcomes, i.e. evaluation of the results that have been delivered by the projects of the second round and, in collaboration with the Communications Team and the relevant Project leader, identify those outcomes that should be highlighted for future use. To increase the possible impact for science, society and policy, the project outcome will be communicated and disseminated to the stakeholders that can make use of them, for instance authorities that are responsible for surveillance systems, laboratories that may be interested to take up procedures for detection or characterization, risk assessors and risk managers.

There will be no Annual Scientific Meeting in Y6, at least not in the format of the ASM in Orvieto, Italy in 2022. Depending on the available resources (budget and time), some scientific meeting may be organised.

2.2.4 WP4

To deliver the scheduled objectives in WP4 and at the overarching OHEJP level, the following work is planned in Y6:

- Find and contract evaluators for JIP-6 COVRIN and arrange for the evaluation of this project.
- Send the final reports from JIPs CARE, OH-Harmony-CAP and MATRIX for evaluation.
- Continued supervision and monitoring of COVRIN, which ends 31st of March 2023.
- Include the final report from COVRIN in D4.29 5th periodic report on JIPs and contribute to the 12M Periodic report Y5.
- Summarize the external evaluations and include them in D4.28 Final reports of 2nd call JIPs and evaluation reports and D4.31 Final report JIP COVRIN and evaluation report, respectively.
- Find and contract external evaluators for the performed OHEJP exercise, SimEx.
- Finalize the D4.30 Report on the OHEJP exercise (SimEx), including the evaluation.
- Make sure all publications from JIPs are uploaded on Zenodo and that they agree with the OHEJP Scientific Publication Policy.
- The OHEJP DMP should be finalized and uploaded on Zenodo.
- Make sure all projects, JIPs and JIPs, have uploaded their final version on Zenodo.
- Finalize the overarching OHEJP DMP and upload it to Zenodo.
- Contribute to the collective work of all the WPs in the dissemination of the scientific results.
- Contribute to the drafting of the OHEJP SPR Y6 and of the final report.
- If relevant WP4 will together with WP3 and WP6 organize a webinar series targeted to OHEJP partners to further present the outputs to the institutes.
- Give input and present results at the SSB meeting, the PMC/POC meeting and to stakeholders.

2.2.5 WPS

During the sixth year, the actions foreseen in WP5 support the end of the OHEJP, and focus on targeted dissemination, sustainability and advocacy.

Targeted dissemination of results will be coupled with depiction of how OHEJP activities close stakeholders' knowledge gaps. This is to be achieved only by the well-established, smooth communication between the OHEJP and various stakeholders. The Stakeholders Committee reached its optimal form, as a cross-sectoral European and international high level forum. Y6 will see the 11th and last Stakeholders Committee meeting (SCMs), which will mostly focus on the impact that the OHEJP achieved and will continue to achieve after its formal end, thus supporting sustainability.

WP5 will advocate consideration of OHEJP results in the stakeholders' policies and initiatives – and the One Health approach in general – supporting stakeholders with regular and ad hoc activities as the occasion arises. To link the stakeholders' identified needs with the outcomes of the OHEJP, WP5 will disseminate results of research and integrative activities following tailored approaches to maximize efficient uptake.

Important tools of targeted dissemination will be the Dissemination Workshop and the Stakeholder Conference. The Dissemination Workshop is part of a Dissemination Workshop series, organised in collaboration with WP4, WP3 and WP6. These workshops are targeted mainly to policy/decision makers at the national level, and focus on specific topics identified by the stakeholders themselves for being of particular interest. One more workshop will be organised in Y6.

The Stakeholder Conference will be a standalone event to highlight the impact that One Health EJP can have not just at the scientific and policy level, but also from the societal and economic point of view. Part of the event will be in fact targeted to sectors like the industry and private sector.

In addition, WP5 will keep its other traditional activities in place: the aforementioned organisation of one SCM, writing of one final targeted report to Key EU Stakeholders, curation of the OHOI and of the DMP, supporting other WPs in dissemination and sustainability activities, and overall liaising with stakeholders' organisations.

2.2.6 WP6

In the sixth year, the following WP6 deliverables will be submitted if they have not been already: D6.13 (Report of the third CPD module in one health), D6.15 & 20 (Report on outputs of the short term missions for the 5th year), D6.16 (Report n°4 on the ASM Satellite Workshop), D6.17 (Report of the 2022 One health summer school), D6.18 (Thesis Reports of 17 PhD studentships), and D6.19 (Report of the 2022 CPD module in one health).

In the sixth year, WP6 will continue to support and monitor the progress and dissemination activities of the PhD candidates and their projects through submission of their project deliverables and publications. WP6 will ensure that the PhD deliverables submission, dissemination, and reporting procedures are adhered to, along with the scientific publication policy. WP6 will support the PhD projects with completion of their final thesis reports which inform the Summary Progress Report Y6, and D6.18- thesis or final thesis reports of 16 PhD studentships (plus the associated 17th PhD student). WP6 will continue to work closely the communications team to support the PhD project outputs, outcomes, tools, reports, and publications are disseminated to the appropriate target audiences in a timely fashion, and in an engaging and suitable format for the target audience.

PhD candidates will continue to be encouraged to join other students, junior and senior researchers and professionals attending or participating in the remaining WP6 activities and other OHEJP activities towards building the next generation of 'One Health' researchers. Through these opportunities, PhD candidates will have the opportunity to expand their professional network and build on the collaborative interactions available.

WP6 will monitor the progress of the Short-Term Missions that took place in the fifth year, finalising reports and working with the communications team to convey the main outcomes of the missions and testimonials from the awardees on the OHEJP website through visually attractive branded case studies. The deliverable D6.20 will be submitted in M60 and will contain the reports of all the missions. This will be uploaded on Zenodo and disseminated on our website and the OHEJP internal and external communication channels.

In addition, reports summarising the final ASM Satellite Workshop, Summer School, and CPD module will be finalised. The WP6 team and Communications Team will share outputs and testimonials to the appropriate target audiences in a timely fashion, and in an engaging and suitable format.

The WP6 and Communications team will continue to work together to identify new and improved ways of disseminating the successes of WP6 not only to our internal target audiences, but also to our external target audiences such as the external scientific advisory board, stakeholders, programme owners and researchers outside our consortium. In addition, the two teams will collaborate their efforts to increase the engagement when disseminating PhD scientific research progress by fostering a diverse and more engaging strategy through the OHEJP's communication channels.

2.2.7 WP7

In collaboration with other WPs the SRIA (D7.2) will be completed and disseminated in collaboration with the Communications Team. A Road map for institutionalisation of One Health, produced in M58 to outline the necessary steps, the risks and opportunities for further institutionalisation of One Health as it relates to the scope of the EJP (D7.4 Document on institutionalisation of One Health) will serve as a basis for a workshop to be organised in Y6 with One Health EJP beneficiaries and key EU institutions in order to identify actions to be taken to strengthen the development achieved by integrative activities during the course of the EJP to ensure they are maintained for the future.

2.2.8 Timing of the different programmed activities and their components

GANTT CHART																
WP	Task	Subtask	Title	M61	M62	M63	M64	M65	M66	M67	M68	M69				
WP1	1.1		Management of EC contractual obligations												1.31	
	1.2		Project management													
	1.3		Organisation of EJP management and governance meetings	PMT		SSB		PMT	ESAB	PMT					FM	
	1.4		Communication tools													
		1.4.0		Communication groups												
		1.4.1		Web site/interface											1.21	
		1.4.2		Internal communications											1.19	
		1.4.3		External communications: Press releases												
		1.4.4		External communications: Professional social networks												
		1.4.5		Special issue on One Health-Zoonoses for a scientific journal										1.22		
	1.4.6		External communications: Merchandise and branding										1.20			
	1.4.7		Annual and final report													
WP2	2.1	2.1.1	Identification and updating of priority research and integrative topics													
		2.1.2	Development and updating of the strategic research agenda													
	2.2	2.2.1	Identification of relevant EU-projects and initiatives													
		2.2.2	Strategic interactions with EU projects and initiatives													
WP3	3.1		Guidelines for project coordinators to report + request extension													
			Updated guidelines for Submission and selection of project proposals													
			Guidelines for WP3/WP4 to monitor projects (JRP&JIP) (at start, Updated guidelines for Evaluation of proposal + Selection of projects													
			Guidelines for WP3/WP4 on the evaluation of final reports													
	3.2	3.2.2	Follow up of recently started projects													
		3.2.3	Monitoring: mid- and end-term reports											3.21		
		3.2.4	Evaluation of JRP reports by external experts: final report											3.20		
	3.3		Second call for projects: Evaluation of full proposals													
		3.4.1	Protocol for Annual Scientific Meeting organisation													
	3.4	3.4.2	Abstract book for Annual Scientific Meeting (ASM)													
4.1.1		Guidelines for submission and selection of JIP proposals														
WP4	4.1	4.1.2	Instructions for reporting on, and monitoring of, JIP progress													
		4.1.3	Guidelines for final evaluation of JIPs													
		4.2.1	Start-up support													
	4.2	4.2.2	Project monitoring											4.29		
		4.2.3	Final evaluations											4.28	4.31	
		4.3.1	Alignment with strategic initiatives at EU level													
	4.3	4.3.2	Support function for integration of additional partners in ongoing JIPs													
		4.3.3	Scientific meetings to enhance integration													
		4.4.1	Call for letters of intent													
	4.4	4.4.2	Prepare output from external peer review for project selection													
		4.5.1	Development of the Data Management Plan													
		4.5.2	Guidance and support for the implementation of the DMP													
	4.5	4.5.3	Open data access point													
		4.6.3	Evaluation of the SimEx											4.30		
		WP5	5.1	5.1.1	Communication links with international stakeholders											
5.1.2	Communication links with national stakeholders															
5.2	5.2.1		Platform for interaction													
	5.2.2		Systematic screening													
	5.2.3		Consolidation of results													
5.3	5.3.1		Capacity map													
	5.3.2		Scientific support to enhance exploitation of results													
5.4	5.4.1		Dissemination strategy													
	5.4.2		Targeted communication													
	5.4.3	Stakeholder conference													5.11	
WP6	6.1		Short term missions													
	6.2		Workshop programme													
	6.3		One health' Summer School for medical and veterinary science													
	6.4		Doctoral training programme												6.18	
6.5		One-Health CPD Module										6.13				
6.6		Communications workshop and media training														
WP7	7.1		Collection of end user Stakeholders' Needs and Expectations.													
	7.2		Definition of the One Health SRIA 2021-2030													
	7.4		Definition of the road map for institutionalization of One Health across													

2.2.9 Detailed work description

2.2.9.1 Annual work plan activities

2.2.9.1.1 WP1-Coordination and Management

Set of activity	WP1- Coordination and Management					Lead Beneficiary			P01-Anses	
						Deputy Lead Beneficiary			P04-Sciensano	
Start month: M1					End month: M69					
Annual period of the OHEJP the project description applies: M61-M69 (Y6)										
Partici pant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Agas	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU
PM	43.08	0	4.58	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Partici pant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRA	IP	APHA	PHE
PM	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Partici pant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	WbVR	FHI
PM	34.4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Partici pant	33	34	35	36	37	39	40	41	42	43
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	SLV	FOHM	SVA	NMVRVI	ISCI
PM	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Partici pant	44	45	46	47						
	BIOR	RUOKA	THL	NEBIH						
PM	0	0	0	0						

Objectives

T1.1: To carry out the EC contractual obligations regarding legal, financial and administrative management and coordination of the EJP.

T1.2: To ensure efficient project management

T1.3: To organize EJP management meetings of all the governance and management bodies of the EJP:

T1.4: To set up and put in place and manage efficient communication tools

Description of programmed activities

Task 1.1: Management of EC contractual obligations

The Coordination Team (CT) will supervise the preparation and submission of the deliverables due from M61 to M69 to the Research Executive Agency (REA). At the beginning of the period, the CT will carry out the annual technical and financial reporting. In addition, the CT will coordinate the preparation, compilation and submission to the EC of the Summary Progress Report (SPR) for sixth year. At the end of the period, the Support Team will prepare the final report.

Task 1.2 Project management

The Coordination Team will exchange on a weekly basis via teleconferences to ensure that administrative, financial and contractual requirements are met. The CT and the PMT will have monthly teleconference to ensure a smooth management and coordination of the WP activities. The CT will also regularly liaise with the REA project officers and report any issue that may arise.

Task 1.3: Organisation of EJP management and governance meetings

The ST will ensure the organisation of all the project governance bodies meetings in regards to the identified planning. There will be 1 SSB, 3 PMT meetings organised, as well as a Final project meeting including a policy event and a press conference.

Task 1-4: Communication tools

Subtask 1.4.0: Communication Groups

Maintain and strengthen working relationships with the PMT, WP5 and Project Leaders to ensure that the OHEJP key outputs and outcomes are disseminated widely and efficiently in the final year to ensure their maximum impact. Maintain and strengthen working relationships with the CCP network, requesting that CCPs copy in the Communications Mailbox during their dissemination to encourage CCP involvement and allows the Communications Team to monitor the progress of dissemination.

Subtask 1.4.1 Web site/interface:

The website is the main information hub of the OHEJP, and the benefits of the website redevelopment involving an external website developer that was conducted in Year 5 will improve website security and stability that needs to be maintained in Year 6. Sustainability of the website will be a key focus in Year 6 as the website needs to exist two years after the end of the One Health EJP. The Communications team will closely collaborate with the Med-Vet-Net Association with respect to sustainable activities and associated responsibilities with their continuation of the website. This will ensure the legacy of the OHEJP research on the site beyond September 2023. The links on the website will be moved from documents stored locally on the website to links that are on Zenodo, a sustainable open access repository.

Subtask 1.4.2 Internal communications:

Newsletters: The Consortium newsletter will be disseminated quarterly to the consortium members. The quarterly will provide updates of the OHEJP events, meetings, research, funding opportunities, education and training activities, and any other information suggested by consortium members or the Communications Team. Each newsletter will be sent by MailChimp as this allows the success of each newsletter to be monitored. These newsletters will also be made available on the OHEJP website under “Newsletters” and advertised on social media accounts. The final external newsletter will be disseminated in the Summer of Year 6 and sent to consortium members and to the OHEJP external mailing list (which is generated on the OHEJP website). The external newsletter is targeted to a wider audience, including the public. Additionally, D.1.19 – annual report on the internal and external newsletters produced during the fifth and sixth years will be submitted.

Subtask 1.4.3 External communications: Press releases

Press releases for OHEJP events will be published on the OHEJP website and advertised on the social media platforms. Press releases for the One Health EJP Stakeholders Conference in Spring Year 6, One Health EJP Policy Event in M69 and Work Package 6 activities will be the responsibility of the hosting institute. The Communications Team will facilitate in the dissemination of this information by the OHEJP.

Subtask 1.4.4 External communications: Professional Social Networks:

The social media platforms are expected to grow, and this growth will be monitored against KPIs in the Communications Strategy to ensure that we are meeting our goals. The key objective for the social media networks is to increase the numbers of followers, impressions, and engagements with our content. This continues our work on developing a One Health Community on social media and reaching a global audience. Advertising and live tweeting of One Health EJP events, including WP6 education and training activities, and linking our posts to external social media campaigns, such as World One Health Day, will raise the profile of the One Health EJP and encourage online engagement.

Subtask 1.4.5 Special issue on One Health-Zoonoses for a scientific journal:

This will be completed in summer 2023 (M66) with the assistance of PMT and OHEJP Project Leaders to be submitted to a peer-reviewed journal in the One Health field.

Subtask 1.4.6 External communications: Merchandise and branding:

Continuing to strengthen the brand will be essential in the sixth year as this will play a significant role in the sustainability of the OHEJP at the end of its final year. The Communications Team will continue to work closely with all consortium members to ensure that significant outcomes are disseminated using branded interactive pdf documents that can continue to be disseminated by OHEJP stakeholders to ensure the legacy lives beyond the five-year programme. The One Health EJP Stakeholders Conference and One Health EJP Policy Event will both be excellent platforms to showcase our consortium and all outcomes to these varied audiences.

Subtask 1.4.7 Annual and final report:

The annual and final reports will be completed in Year 6.

Task 1.5 Ethics

Task 1.6 Declaration of Cofund

N/A

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D1.19	Annual report on the internal and external newsletter produced during the fifth and sixth year	69

D1.20	Complete version of annual and final reports for stakeholders n°5	67
D1.21	Submit report on sustainability of website	69
D1.22	Submit a special issue on One Health to a relevant journal	66 (new delivery date to be introduced in the next AMD to the GA)
D1.19	Annual report on the internal and external newsletter produced during the fifth and sixth year	69
Milestones		
Ref	Title	Due month
N/A		

2.2.9.1.2 WP2-Strategic Research Agenda

Set of Activity	WP2–Strategic Research Agenda				Lead Beneficiary			P30-RIVM		
					Deputy Lead Beneficiary			P17-UCM		
Start month: M1					End month: M69					
Annual period of the OHEJP the project description applies: M61-M69 (Y6)										
Partici pant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
		Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BFR	FLI	RKI
PM										
Partici pant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRA	IP	APHA	PHE
PM					0.75					
Partici pant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	Wbvr	FHI
PM								0.75		
Partici pant	33	34	35	36	37	39	40	41	42	43
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	SLV	FOHM	SVA	NMVRVI	ISCIH
PM										
Partici pant	44	45	46	47						
	BIOR	RUOKA	THL	NEBIH						
PM										
Objectives										
T2.1: Start developing the strategic research and innovation agenda (SRIA)										
T2.2: Update de EU-projects/initiatives and strategic interactions with EU-projects										

Description of programmed activities

All deliverables of WP2 will have been delivered by the end of Y5. WP2 will provide input for the strategy on sustainability developed in WP7. Also, WP2 will provide input for the OHEJP dissemination plans regarding the main outputs of the project during all these years.

Task 2.1: Development of the SRA

Task Leader: RIVM

Deputy Task Leader: UCM

Participants: all partner organisations

In Y6 Task 2.1 will continue to monitor relevant scientific developments and provide input for the strategy on sustainability developed in WP7.

Task 2.2: Strategic interactions with EU projects and initiatives

Task Leader: UCM

Deputy Task Leader: RIVM

Participants: Anses, Sciensano, BfR, SVA

Task 2.2 will not be pursued in Y6

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
N/A		

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
N/A		

2.2.9.1.3 WP3-Management of Joint Research Projects

Set of Activity	WP3-Joint Research Projects management					Lead Beneficiary				P04-Sciensano
						Deputy Lead Beneficiary				P31-WR
Start month: M1					End month: M69					
Annual period of the OHEJP the project description applies: M61-M69 (Y6)										
Participatant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BFR	FLI	RKI	DTU
PM			15.58							
Participatant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRA	IP	APHA	PHE
PM	1.0									
Participatant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UOS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	Wbvr	FHI
PM										
Participatant	33	34	35	36	37	39	40	41	42	43
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	SLV	FOHM	SVA	NMVRVI	ISCIH
PM										
Participatant	44	45	46	47						
	BIOR	RUOKA	THL	NEBIH						
PM										
<p>Objectives</p> <p>Task 3.1: Drawing up of guidelines for submission, selection and evaluation of JRP proposals as well as request of extension of accepted JRPs.</p> <p>Task 3.2: Supervision of the JRP in the first round of projects</p> <p>Task 3.3: Organisation of a second round of projects and their supervision.</p> <p>Task 3.4: Organisation of annual scientific meetings (ASM) where results from JRP are presented</p>										

Description of programmed activities

Task 3.1: Drawing up of guidelines for submission, selection and evaluation of JRP proposals as well as request of extension of accepted JRPs. Task with input from WP4 (Joint Integrative Projects) and with WP6 (Education and Training)

All guidelines concerning WP3 have been delivered in Y1 and Y2. This task has ended.

Task 3.2: Supervision of the JRP in the first round of projects

Subtask 3.2.1 Periodic follow up of activities in the JRP consortia

All JRP of the first round have terminated their activities in Y4. This task has ended.

Subtask 3.2.2 Follow-up of recently started projects

All second round JRP started in 2020. This task has ended.

Subtask 3.2.3: Mid- and end-term evaluations; monitoring of the KPI, deliverables and milestones detailed in the annual JRP reports

In Y6, WP3 will organize the evaluation of the final JRP reports, expected in December 2022. Subsequently, WP3 will contribute to the drafting of the Periodic One Health EJP Report Y5 and the Periodic JRP Report Y5.

Subtask 3.2.4: End-term evaluations by external experts: final report

The Final JRP Reports, together with the evaluation reports by the external experts, will be published in Y6.

Task 3.3: Organisation of a second round of projects and their supervision. Task with help from WP4.

This task and its subtasks is finalised in Y2.

Task 3.4: Organisation of annual scientific meetings (ASM) where results from JRP are presented

Subtask 3.4.1: Protocol for organisation of annual scientific meetings

This subtask is finalised in Y1.

Subtask 3.4.2: Organisation of ASM, scientific part

The ASM2022 was the last scientific meeting that was planned under One Health EJP.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D3.20	Final reports of 2nd callJRPs and evaluation reports	65
D3.21	5th periodic report onJRPs	63

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
N/A		

2.2.9.1.4 WP4–Management of Joint Integrative Projects

Set of Activity	WP4–Joint Integrative Projects										Lead Beneficiary		P41-SVA
											Deputy Lead Beneficiary		P36- INSA
Start month: M1						End month: M60							
Annual period of the OHEJP the project description applies: M61-M69 (Y6)													
Partici pant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12			
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU			
PM			1.13										
Partici pant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22			
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRA	IP	APHA	PHE			
PM													
Partici pant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32			
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVMI	WBVR	FHI			
PM													
Partici pant	33	34	35	36	37	39	40	41	42	43			
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	SLV	FOHMI	SVA	NMV/RVI	ISCIII			
PM				1.5				9					
Partici pant	44	45	46	47									
	BIOR	RUOKA	THL	NEBIH									
PM													
Objectives													
T4.1: To develop guidelines for evaluation of final reports and keep already produced guidelines on JIP reporting up to date.													
T4.2: To follow and support the launch and implementation of the JIPs from the 1st and 2 nd call.													
T4.3: To support the alignment of EJP activities with two external EU initiatives/projects, and to support internal integration through the arrangement of integrative missions and a thematic workshop.													
T4.4: n/a													

T4.5: To provide support and follow the implementation of the Data Management Plan (DMP), and ensure alignment with the overarching dissemination plan.

Description of programmed activities

Task 4.1 Development of procedures and guidelines for submission and selection of JIP proposals, and for reporting and evaluation.

Subtask 4.1.1 Guidelines for submission and selection of JIP proposals

N/A

Subtask 4.1.2 Instructions for reporting on, and monitoring of JIP progress

An updated template will be provided to COVRIN for the final report

Subtask 4.1.3 Guidelines for evaluation of JIPs

Updated guidelines will be provided for the external assessors evaluating the JIPs finalizing in Y5 and Y6.

Task 4.2 Supervision of JIPs

Subtask 4.2.1 Start-up support

N/A

Subtask 4.2.2 Project monitoring

The JIP COVRIN will be supported by the WP4 Team during its final months. The project ends 31st of March. There will be regular contact with the project leaders and reminders about upcoming deliverables and reports. WP4 representatives will participate in the final meeting. The final report of COVRIN, will be part of D4.29 5th periodic report on JIPs.

In collaboration with the OHEJP Communication team and other OHEJP WPs, it will be discussed how the results from the JIPs can be further disseminated.

It will be made sure that all publications from JIPs are uploaded on Zenodo and that they agree with the OHEJP Scientific Publication Policy.

Subtask 4.2.3 Final evaluations

The JIPs finalized in Y5 and Y6 will be evaluated by three external assessors each. These assessors will be recruited and contracted. We strive for one evaluator who have assessed the original proposal, one new scientific evaluator and one PMC/POC member for each project. The external evaluations will be summarized and included in D4.28 Final reports of 2nd call JIPs and evaluation reports and D4.31 Final report JIP COVRIN and evaluation report, respectively.

Present the results of the evaluations at meetings with SSB, stakeholders and PMC/POC.

Task 4.3 Integrative support

Subtask 4.3.1 Alignment with strategic initiatives at EU level

Follow-up discussions will be performed with SISOT, for the possible inclusion of additional tools from the JIPs.

Subtask 4.3.2 Support function for integration of additional partners in ongoing JIPs

N/A

Subtask 4.3.3 Scientific meetings to enhance and leverage integration

N/A

Task 4.4 Organisation of call for additional JIPs for the period Y3-Y5

N/A

Task 4.5 Open data management

The overarching OHEJP DMP will be finalized and uploaded on Zenodo.

Subtask 4.5.1 Development of the Data Management Plan

The overarching OHEJP DMP will be finalized and uploaded on Zenodo. We will make sure that the project DMPs can be found on Zenodo and that all deliverables are open access.

Subtask 4.5.2 Guidance and support for the implementation of the DMP

All overarching WPs will be guided on how to fulfill the overarching DMP.

Support will be provided to the recently finished projects on how to complete and upload their final DMPs.

Subtask 4.5.3 Open data access point

DMPs can be accessed by The Outcome Inventory provided by WP5.

Task 4.6 OHEJP Exercise (SimEx)

Subtask 4.6.1 Planning of the exercise

N/A

Subtask 4.6.2 Effectuation of the exercise

N/A

Subtask 4.6.3 Evaluation of the exercise

In addition to the already produced internal assessment of SimEx, an external assessment will be performed. An assessment protocol will be produced with the input from the external SimEx Advisory Board and three external evaluators will be recruited and contracted. The results from the external evaluation will be included in D4.30 Report on the OHEJP exercise SimEx.

The final report from SimEx will be completed and uploaded on Zenodo.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D4.28	Final reports of 2nd call JIPs and evaluation reports on evaluation of finalised JIPs, 2nd round	65
D4.29	5th periodic report on JIPs	63
D4.30	Report on the OHEJP exercise SimEx	63
D4.31	Final report of JIP COVRIN and evaluation report	66

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
N/A		

2.2.9.1.5 WP5-Science to policy translation

Set of Activity	WP5-Science to policy translation					Lead Beneficiary			P09-BfR	
						Deputy Lead Beneficiary			P13-SSI	
Start month : M1						End month : M69				
Annual period of the OHEJP the project description applies: M61-M69 (Y6)										
Partici pant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU
PM							11			
Partici pant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRA	IP	APHA	PHE
PM	7.5									
Partici pant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RVM	Wbvr	FHI
PM										
Partici pant	33	34	35	36	37	39	40	41	42	43
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	SLV	FOHMI	SVA	NMVRVI	ISCIII
PM										
Partici pant	44	45	46	47						
	BIOR	RUOKA	THL	NEBIH						
PM										
Objectives:										
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To broaden the interaction with stakeholders, covering national, EU and international interests - To follow the established procedures for a good information flow and interaction between the OHEJP projects and national, EU and international stakeholders to support complementarity and synergy of activities and exploitation of results - To regularly update research and integrative needs of stakeholders identified in policy processes and to keep the interaction with the OHEJP consortium - To regularly integrate available science and activities and support alignment for closure of knowledge gaps of international stakeholders - To support identification of potential for synergies between OHEJP activities and other international projects by supporting communication and disseminating actively results 										

- To foster dissemination of results from activities within the OHEJP following the targeted dissemination policy initiatives addressing the protection of consumers health

Description of programmed activities :

Task 5.1: Identification of the stakeholders and establishment of communication links

Subtask 5.1.1 Establish communication links with EU and international stakeholders

- Links with EU and international stakeholders are well consolidated, and one important occasion to meet with representatives of Stakeholders Committee organisations will be the 11th Stakeholders Committee meetings (SCM, subtask 5.4.2).
- WP5 will actively update Key EU stakeholders (ECDC and EFSA) and other EU and international stakeholders (EEA, EMA, FAO, WOH, WHO-Euro) regarding the scientific and integrative output of the consortium through the 8th Targeted Report (subtask 5.4.2) and specific workshops (subtask 5.3.2).
- Stakeholders will be involved and actively engaged in sustainability aspects of the OHEJP.
- Interested parties not traditionally included in the Stakeholders Committee (e.g. research institutes, professionals' associations, initiatives, and private sector) will be approached taking advantage of contact taken through networking activities of previous years, and encouraged to join the Stakeholder Conference (subtask 5.4.3).

Subtask 5.1.2 Establish communication links to national stakeholders

- Interaction with national stakeholders will be consolidated by applying the OHEJP Outcome Inventory (subtask 5.3.1), the Data Management Plan Reader (subtask 5.4.1) and by communicating outcomes and achievements of the OHEJP as well as identified synergies and activities complementary to the OHEJP.
- Awareness on the outcomes of the OHEJP will be raised at national stakeholders' forums like the POC-PMC meeting and the SSB meeting.
- A final Dissemination Workshop (subtask 5.3.2) will be held in Y6, and like all Dissemination Workshops will be targeted specifically at national stakeholders.

Task 5.2: Identification of the research needs of EU stakeholders

Subtask 5.2.1 Platform for interaction

- WP5 will actively collaborate with the stakeholders to maintain the consolidated way in which the needs and support requests are identified and communicated, in order to keep the process timely and flexible.
- Dynamic and timely communication within the OHEJP and with the stakeholders will be continued through the use of the virtual groups of the OHEJP website and, most importantly, by personal communications including appointed representatives.
- Main platform for interaction will be the SCM (subtask 5.4.2).
- Consolidation of research and integrative needs of the EU stakeholders will be continued to provide specific support and input for the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA).

Subtask 5.2.2 Systematic screening

- Regular and systematic screening of stakeholders' documents will be carried on. In Y6 important aims of such activity will be to:
 - Identify probable future needs and knowledge gaps of the stakeholders to support the sustainability of the OHEJP (including the SRIA, led by WP7).
 - Keep the consortium up to date with upcoming EU regulations and strategies.
 - Identify emerging risks.

- Identify opportunities to support EU and international stakeholders (e.g. consultations, expert advices, stakeholders' contributions).
 - Identify stakeholders' knowledge gaps that are being already addressed by the OHEJP
- The list of website screened will be continuously updated as websites are put down, or new websites are launched online.
 - WP5 will keep publishing monthly documents summarising the outcomes of the activity "scanning of stakeholders' documents" and making them available to consortium members and stakeholders.
 - Systematic screening activities will be integrated by intelligence from private communications

Subtask 5.2.3 Consolidation of results

- Scientific output of the OHEJP will be collected and mapped against the outcomes of the systematic screening. The result will be regularly discussed with the stakeholders (task 5.1 and task 5.4).
- Stakeholders' identified research and integrative needs will be used to update the Strategic Research Agenda (SRIA), a task led by WP7.
- Request of support by the stakeholders, being it scientific (subtask 5.3.2) or non-scientific, will be considered, discussed within the consortium, and ad hoc action to address stakeholders' needs will be taken as appropriate.
- Additional opportunities to support stakeholders, to advocate consideration of OHEJP results in the stakeholders' policies and activities, and to advocate the One Health approach in general will be identified thanks to systematic screening (subtask 5.2.2) and direct communication. Action will be taken when appropriate.

Task 5.3: Linking of the scientific capacity available in the EJP with the stakeholders' identified needs: closure of knowledge gaps

Subtask 5.3.1 Capacity map

The One Health EJP Outcome Inventory (OHOI, formerly referred to as "capacity map") is an important tool for highlighting expertise, outcomes and updates of the OHEJP and of its activities, in particular JIPs, JRPs and PhDs. It allows broad dissemination of results of the various activities within the consortium and depicts to some extent complementarity with activities outside the OHEJP. Given its public nature, the OHOI targets not just the key EU stakeholders, but also national, international stakeholders, and any interested party (e.g. other One Health initiatives, private sector), and supports internal collaboration and dissemination. During the sixth year focus will be put on the following topics:

- One major final update of content will be carried out. Requests on a case base from projects' representatives will always be considered.
- Comments from the users will be taken into consideration to improve content and navigation.
- WP5 will continue interacting with WP4 to avoid duplication of work between the OHOI and Data Management Plan (DMP, a task led by WP4), and to maintain the appropriate linking between the two systems
- WP5 will support sustainability of the OHOI after the end of the OHEJP by discussing the best way to make information easily findable and available, and by adapting the OHOI accordingly
- The OHOI will be moved to the website of the MedVetNet association to keep the database publicly available after the end of the OHEJP

Subtask 5.3.2:Scientific support to stakeholders

- Procedures to provide scientific support will be put in place by means discussed in the SCM (subtask 5.4.2).
- One final Dissemination Workshop will be organised in collaboration with WP3, WP4 and WP6. Dissemination workshops are a format optimised during Y4 and Y5. They:
 - Are centred on specific topics identified by the stakeholders at the national, EU, and international level for being of particular interest.
 - Highlight OHEJP developed solutions and how the presented solutions are used (or could potentially be used) in real life situations.
 - Target preferably policy/decision makers and risk managers at the national level, however, as the solution presented can have an impact at the EU and international level as well, EU and international organisations are welcome to take part.
 - A report is distributed after the workshop and made publicly available by uploading on Zenodo and by providing the link on the OHEJP website for easy findability.
- The format of the Dissemination Workshop will be further improved by considering feedback from past workshops.
- Opportunity for further scientific support to stakeholders will be identified by systematic screening (subtask 5.2.2) and direct communication, and requests for support will be disseminated internally to the OHEJP to the appropriate audience.
- Allocation of resources to support specific stakeholders' needs with specific actions (ad hoc support) will be continued. One possibility would be organising projects' visits at stakeholders' organisations.

Task 5.4: Dissemination of new knowledge, tools and materials

Subtask 5.4.1 Dissemination strategy

WP5 will concentrate its efforts to disseminate scientific and integrative outputs in a targeted way, to meet the stakeholders' identified needs:

- The OHOI (subtask 5.3.1) will be updated and further developed to list scientific updates in a tidy and well-ordered way, and in the light of future moving on the MedVetNet Association website. Information and updates of the OHOI will be disseminated when necessary to increase visibility.
- A final Targeted Report (subtask 5.4.2) will be distributed to European and international stakeholders and dissemination internal to the stakeholders' organisations will be encouraged.
- A report of the final Dissemination Workshop (subtask 5.3.2) will be sent to the participants to the workshop, made publicly available by uploading on Zenodo, and made findable by linking it to the OHEJP website
- The dissemination strategy will be discussed in the 11th SCM (subtask 5.4.2).
- A final Dissemination Workshop (subtask 5.3.2) will be organised considering stakeholders' needs, targeting policy/decision makers, and depicting practical solutions.
- The DMP reader (led by WP4) will be curated in collaboration with WP4 and with the company providing the software to allow public access to DMP data.
- WP5, in collaboration with WP4, will ensure that the DMPs of the JRPs and JIPs are publicly available through Zenodo and easily findable through the OHEJP website to maximise FAIRness.

Subtask 5.4.2 Targeted communication

- Regarding the Targeted Report to Key EU Stakeholders:
 - A last Targeted Report will be distributed to EU and international stakeholders one month before the 11th SCM.
 - Focus will be given on those topics of highest interests for ECDC and EFSA, including selected OHEJP events.

- To give visibility also to projects not directly selected by ECDC and EFSA, brief summaries of all scientific publications produced by the OHEJP will be given.
 - Summaries of solutions produced by all finalised OHEJP projects will be added in each report.
 - The report will facilitate linkage with external resources in case more insights are needed.
 - Although targeted mostly at ECDC and EFSA, it will be distributed also to the other stakeholders' organisations (EEA, EMA, FAO, OIE, WHO-Euro) and internal dissemination will be encouraged.
- The 11th and last Stakeholders Committee Meeting (SCM) will be organized:
- Focus will be put on disseminating OHEJP outcomes to support consideration of OHEJP results in stakeholders' policies.
 - The SCM will be a forum to bring around the table all the stakeholders' organisations, and to involve them in sustainability aspects of the OHEJP (e.g. SRIA). Other topics and points of discussion will be incorporated in the agenda as needs emerge.
 - One month before the 11th SCM background documents (e.g. the Targeted Report) will be distributed to the meeting's participants.

Subtask 5.4.3 Stakeholder conference

- The Stakeholder Conference will be a standalone event organised in Y6.
- It will be one of the most important forum for interaction with a broad range of stakeholders (not limited to the Stakeholders Committee).
- The aim of the event will be to highlight the impact and potential impact of OHEJP-developed solutions at the policy and scientific level, but also to some extent at the economic and social level. It will also be an opportunity to discuss on the science-policy interface for One Health, and to explore additional opportunities and challenges concerning the uptake of One Health EJP solutions from the stakeholders.
- This two-day event will take place after the finalisation of OHEJP projects, in order to have all the deliverables and outcomes available and to allow maximum exploitation of results.
- One part will be addressed at policy and decision makers at the national, EU and international level, to highlight the impact and the potential impact of OHEJP-developed solution, and to encourage the stakeholders to pick them up.
- One part will focus on a wider scope of stakeholders, including research institutes, projects, initiatives, and private sector, to highlight the potential impact and benefit that OHEJP-developed solution can have at the societal, economic and industry level.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D5.10	Fifth annual report on dissemination activities to international stakeholders	60
D5.11	Report on a stakeholder conference	68

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
MS77	Stakeholder conference	68

2.2.9.1.6 WP6-Training and Education

Set of Activity	WP6-Training and Education										Lead Beneficiary	P23-UoS
											Deputy Lead Beneficiary	P31-WbvR
Start month : M1							End month : M69					
Annual period of the OHEJP the project description applies: M61-M69 (Y6)												
Partici pant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12		
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU		
PM												
Partici pant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22		
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRA	IP	APHA	PHE		
PM												
Partici pant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32		
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	WbvR	FHI		
PM	12.4								1.2			
Partici pant	33	34	35	36	37	39	40	41	42	43		
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	SLV	FOHM	SVA	NMVRVI	ISCI		
PM												
Partici pant	44	45	46	47								
	BIOR	RUOKA	THL	NEBIH								
PM												

Objectives

- T6.1: Short Term Missions
- T6.2: Workshop programme (satellite to Annual Scientific Meetings)
- T6.3: One health' Summer School for medical and veterinary science undergraduates
- T6.4: Doctoral Training Programme
- T6.5: One-Health Continuing Professional Development (CPD) Module
- T6.6: Communications workshop and media training

Description of programmed activities

Task 6.1: Short Term Missions

For those that have not already done so to complete their missions. To share scientific expertise, knowledge, facilities, and methodologies to harmonise approaches in the area of Foodborne Zoonoses (FBZ), Antimicrobial Resistance (AMR), and Emerging Threats (ET). Reports for each of these short term missions will be provided, and summaries and testimonials from each of these missions will be made available on the One Health EJP website.

Applications for five (including one co-application) short term missions to be completed in 2022-2023 are still being evaluated and therefore details are not presented. The Report on outputs of the short term missions (D6.15) will be submitted by 28 February 2023.

Task 6.2: Workshop programme (satellite to Annual Scientific Meetings)

The Report on one workshop per year associated with ASM (with WP1, 3, 4 and 5) (D6.16) will be submitted by 31st December 2022. This workshop focused on the use of rapid and innovative diagnostics for pathogen and antimicrobial resistance detection in clinical and environmental settings. Additionally, the workshop illustrated the background of two key mobile diagnostics platforms: LAMP and LEC-LAMP, their application in diagnostics, advantages compared to conventional assays and to discuss current challenges. LAMP is a rapid loop-mediated isothermal amplification approach used to detect target nucleic acids; while LEC-LAMP is a recently developed modified LAMP assay that can facilitate single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) identification and multiplex target detection. The workshop also provided the opportunity for a hands-on in-silico approach to the design of diagnostic assays using LAMP and LEC-LAMP platforms, with the focus on targeting zoonotic pathogens and antimicrobial resistance genes.

Task 6.3: ‘One health’ Summer School for medical and veterinary science undergraduates

A proposal for the 2022 summer school is to be submitted by the University of Surrey to potentially take place in November 2022. The Report of the fourth One health summer school will be written up in 2023 (D6.17).

Task 6.4: Doctoral Training Programme

All PhD candidates will be finalising their projects and writing up their thesis in Y6 if they have not done so already. Additionally, final thesis reports will be submitted by students/supervisors, and this final thesis report (D6.18) is due by 30th June 2023.

Task 6.5: One-Health Continuing Professional Development (CPD) Module

The 2022 CPD module will take place in November 2022 and will focus on rapid diagnostics and harmonisation of diagnostic tests, hosted by the Statens Serum Institut and the Technical University of Denmark. The Report of the third CPD module in one health will be submitted by 28 February 2023.

Task 6.6: Communications workshop and media training

N/A

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D6.13	Report of the third CPD module in one health	62
D6.14	Report n°3 of the annual short term missions completed also uploaded onto theEJP webpage.	62
D6.15	Report on outputs of the short term missions	62

D6.16	Report n°4 on one workshop per year associated with ASM(with WP1,3,4 and 5)	60
D6.17	Report n°4 of the Onehealth summer schoolwith a minimum of 12 delegates	60
D6.18	Thesis Reports of up to17 PhD studentships	66
D6.19	Report of the fourthCPD module in onehealth	60
D6.20	Report n°4 of the annual short term missions completed also uploaded onto theEJP webpage.	62
Milestones		
Ref	Title	Due month
N/A		

2.2.9.1.7 WP7-Sustainability

Set of Activity	WP7-Sustainability										Lead Beneficiary	P27- ISS
											Deputy Lead Beneficiary	P20- IP
Start month: M1										End month: M69		
Annual period of the OHEJP the project description applies: M60-M69 (Y6)												
Partici pant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12		
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU		
PM												
Partici pant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22		
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRA	IP	APHA	PHE		
PM												
Partici pant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32		
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAMI	IZSLER	RIVM	WbVR	FHI		
PM					2							
Partici pant	33	34	35	36	37	39	40	41	42	43		
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	SLV	FOHM	SVA	NMVRVI	ISCI		
PM								2				
Partici pant	44	45	46	47								
	BIOR	RUOKA	THL	NEBIH								
PM												
Objectives												
T7.1: Gathering Stakeholders' Needs and Expectations												
T7.2: Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) 2021-2030 (SRIA 2021-2030);												
T7.3: Making the bridges between EJP's beneficiaries and stakeholders sustainable												
Description of programmed activities												
Task 7.1: Gathering Stakeholders' Needs and Expectations (Task leader BfR/participants: ANSES, IP, ISS, SVA)												

Subtask 7.2.1: Definition of the SRIA in cooperation with WP1, WP2, WP5
Task completed in Y5

Subtask 7.1.1: Mapping the stakeholders at national, European and international stages
Task completed in Y5

Task 7.2: Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA 2021-2030)
Task leader: ISS / Participants: RIVM, ANSES, BfR, IP, SVA UCM.

Subtask 7.2.1: Definition of the SRIA in cooperation with WP1, WP2, WP5
Work completed in Y5

Subtask 7.2.2: definition of the innovation activities to be included in the agenda, taking into account the SRA and the results of task 7.1
Task completed in Y5

Task 7.3: Making the bridges between EJP’s beneficiaries and stakeholders sustainable
Task Leader: SVA / Participants: all beneficiaries

Subtask 7.3.1 Application of framework for evaluation of One Health
Task completed in Y5

Subtask 7.3.2 Institutional analysis
Task completed in Y5

Subtask 7.3.3 Road map for institutionalisation of One Health
Based on the output from preceding tasks, and in collaboration with WP2 and WP4, a high-level workshop will be organised with One Health EJP beneficiaries and key EU institutions in order to identify actions to be taken to strengthen the development achieved by integrative activities during the course of the EJP to ensure they are maintained for the future

Deliverables		
Ref	Title	Due month
N/A		
Milestones		
Ref	Title	Due month
MS101	Workshop on road map for institutionalisation of One Health	M66
MS103	Road map for making the collaborations between One Health partners sustainable	M64

2.2.9.1.1 JIP06- SARS-CoV2 Research Integration and Preparednes-COVRIN

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)	SRA Integrating activities, focussing on detection-/typing methods/protocols, surveillance strategies/signalling.										
Research Project Title	SARS-CoV2 Research Integration and Preparedness										
Research Project Acronym	COVRIN										
Leading Organisation	P31-WBVR			Deputy Organisation			Leading Organisation				P23-UoS
Project Leader	Wim H.M. van der Poel			Deputy Project leader			Daniel Horton				
Project Start month	M40 – March 2021			Project End month			M63 – March 2023				
Annual period of the OHEJP the work plan applies: Y5 and Y6											
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU	
PM	8.90		0.10				0.60	4.23			
Participant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRA	IP	APHA	PHE	
PM				1.0	0.25				2.80		
Participant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	
	UoS	NNK	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	Wbvr	FHI	
PM	1.89				0.75	0.90	0.17	1.83	0.70		
Participant	33	34	35	36	37	39	40	41	42	43	
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	SLV	FOHM	SVA	NMVRVI	ISCI	
PM	1.60	1.86	0.60	0.29				0.77			
Participant	44	45	46	47							
Participant	BIOR	RUOKA	THL	NEBIH							
	0.40										
PM	0.40										
Objectives WPO											
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leading and coordination of COVRIN • Exchange Information between COVRIN work packages 											

- Integration of COVRIN results
- Linking to external partners, other international projects (EU activities) and stakeholder (in particular EC, EFSA, ECDC, EMA)
- Communication about COVRIN activities and results
- Organisation of meetings of COVRIN partners
- Organisation of interactions with stakeholders
- Scoping to avoid overlaps with other (EU-funded) Covid19 activities.

Description of work

WP: 0 Coordination and communication

WP start month: 40

WP end month: 66

WP Leader: WBVR (Wim van der Poel)

WP Deputy: UoS (Daniel Horton)

WP participants: All partners of COVRIN: ANSES (P1), Ages (P2),Sciensano (P4), VRI (P8), BfR(P9), FLI (P10), INIA (P16), UCM (P17), APHA (P21), UoS (P23), ISS (P27), IZSAM (P28), IZSLER (P29), RIVM (P30), WBVR (P31), NVI (P33), PIWET (P34), INIAV (P35), INSA (P36), SVA (P41).

Short description of WP0:

Work package 0 leads and coordinates the COVRIN project. This includes organising Information flows, integration of results, active linking to external partners, projects as well as stakeholder Communication about project activities and outcomes. Organisation of meetings and a scoping to avoid overlaps with other (EU-funded) Covid19 activities.

T0.1:To manage exchange of research data and the information flow between work packages a share point for data exchange will be established. This share-point will be available for all project partners throughout the project for management of information flows and meetings organisation

T0.2: Communication about project activities and project results will be described in an annual report and an end report. These will include communications about results to the scientific community as well as the general public. WP0 will also ensure that all project reports and deliverables will be produced timely.

T0.3: A scoping exercise will be conducted to avoid overlaps with other EU funded COVID19 research activities. Three major project meetings will be organised: First, a face-to-face kick-off meeting will be held with all participants in month M42. Next, a mid-term meeting is planned for all WP-leaders and finally, the final project meeting or conference will be conducted in M63. The latter two meetings will be online or combined with other EJP meetings. Stakeholders (i.e. EC, EFSA, EMA) will be invited to participate in all project meetings.

A communication channel through REA will be established in order to inform the European Commission and EU Agencies (EFSA, ECDC and EMA) on (interim) knowledge/data.

Knowledge/data interim and final results that could serve for potential Covid19-related risk assessment and/or risk management activities, will be communicated to REA and to relevant EU stakeholders (European Commission and EU Agencies EFSA, ECDC and EMA).

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D0.1.2	First management report	M51
D0.2.1	First annual communications report	M51

D0.3.3	Report Mid-term meeting (presentations)	M57
D0.1.3	Second management report	M63
D0.2.2	Second annual communications report (end report)	M63
D0.3.4	Report Project end meeting Presentations)	M60

Objectives WP1

- To assess and assure validity of coronavirus testing
- To optimise molecular detection of SARS-CoV2
- To compare immunological testing for SARS-CoV2
- To better understand how testing relates to the potential for transmission.
- To integrate activities among partners to enhance capability for the detection of SARS-CoV-2 in potential animal hosts and environmental samples
- To determine the survival of virus in these samples from hosts and the environment.
- To assess the bioavailability of SARS-CoV2 in environmental samples to establish the role in infection in susceptible hosts.

Description of work

WP: 1 Detection of SARS-CoV2 in animal reservoirs and hosts, and the environment

WP start month: 40

WP end month: 66

WP Leader: UoS (Daniel Horton)

WP Deputy: FLI (Martin Groschup)

WP participants: ANSES (P1), Ages (P2), Sciensano (P4), VRI(P8), FLI (P10), UCM (P17), APHA (P21), UoS (P23), ISS (P27), IZSAM (P28), IZSLER (P29), RIVM (P30), WBVR (P31), NVI (P33), INIAV (P35), SVA (P41).

Short description of WP1:

Integration of studies on SARS-CoV2 detection in livestock, wildlife, pets and the environment. Optimization and harmonization of RNA and immunological detection methods for SARS-CoV-2 detection in animal and environmental samples. Definition of bioavailability of virus in fomites, water, and the environment

T1.1: SARS-CoV2 genome detection in livestock, wildlife, pets and environmental samples. Data from previous and planned testing for SARS-CoV-2 genomes in animals and in the environment will be compiled and shared (to inform surveillance in WP3). Methods in use will be assessed using published and unpublished comparisons with focus on: Comparison of extraction methods in different clinical animal samples (matrices), PCR and sequencing optimisation. Positive controls will be shared among partners and ring-trials will be organised where necessary to compare methods. These data will include opportunistic sampling in candidate species in the wild, companion animals, in captive livestock and from experimental studies

T1.2: Optimization and harmonization of immunological SARS-CoV2 antigen and antibody detection methods in domestic and wildlife animals. will be compared in terms of their sensitivity and specificity and optimized as appropriate. Matrix effects for swab samples from infected livestock and pets will be studied. Commercially available Point Of Care SARS-CoV-2 antigen tests will be included. Likewise IgM and IgG antibody tests will be compared and assessed in terms of their specificity and sensitivity. Both study lines will include opportunistic sampling in candidate species in companion animals and in captive livestock and from corresponding experimental studies.

T1.3: Definition of bioavailability of virus in fomites, water and in the environment. This task is crucial to interpret the relevance of detecting SARS-CoV-2 in fomites and the environment but also to assess

the infectivity of the virus on these substrates over time, and at different temperatures. Comparison with RNA quantification (PCR versus live virus) will inform risk assessments (in WP3). Results are expected to include viability of live virus in field samples (water, feed, surfaces including animal fur/coats/hide etc) and from experimental studies.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D1.1.1	Report on available data from SARS-CoV-2 virus genome testing in companion animals and livestock	M60
D1.1.2	Report on available data from SARS-CoV-2 virus genome testing in wildlife	M63
D1.3	Report on the bioavailability of virus on fomites, water and the environment	M60
D1.2.1	Report on methods for virus antigen detection in clinical samples from animals	M63
D1.1.3	Report on available data from SARS-CoV-2 genome detection in environmental samples	M63
D1.2.2	Report on available data from antibody testing in livestock, companion animals and wildlife	M63

Objectives WP2

- To characterize SARS-CoV-2 variants
- To map evolutionary changes of SARS-CoV-2 viruses isolated within and across humans and different animal species.
- To assess the risk of zoonotic and reverse zoonotic transmission, potential immune evasion and reinfection based on virus characterizations.
- To determine changes in regions critical for vaccine development (S-gene) or antiviral medication (RdRp).
- To better understand the molecular and biochemical mechanisms underlying angiotensin converting enzyme (ACE)-2 receptor binding, pathogenesis and viral kinetics in host species. Studies in in vitro and ex vivo systems as well as in animal models will be performed.
- To optimise ex-vivo and in-vivo models available at partner institutes.
- To determine if changes in the receptor binding domain leads to alterations in replication and viral release, host cell antiviral responses or pathological effects in relevant host species.

Description of work

WP: 2 SARS-CoV2 Characterization

WP start month: 40

WP end month: 66

WP Leader: APHA (Sharon Brookes)

WP Deputy: IZSAM (Alessio Lorusso)

WP participants: ANSES (P1), FLI (P10), APHA (P21), UoS (P23), ISS (27), IZSAM (P28), IZSLER (P29), WBVR (P31), NVI (P33), PIWET (P34), INIAV (P35), SVA (P41).

Short description of WP2:

Genome analyses; Next generation sequencing of detected isolates and metagenomic sequencing of different samples. In vitro and ex vivo biological characterization of circulating SARS-CoV2 strains. Development, optimization and harmonization of animal models for SARS-CoV2 characterization. Analyses of virus traits related to zoonotic and/or reverse zoonotic transmission.

T2.1: Whole genome sequences by NGS (various methods) of SARS-CoV-2 strains from humans and animals.

- a) Methodologies exchange and harmonisation
Archival samples of wild and domestic animals will be used for CoV RNA detection and NGS.
- b) Sample type (clinical – field or experimental / isolate) and extraction protocols plus validation, Phylogenetic analysis and investigation for potential virulence traits will be performed.
- c) Nucleic acid comparisons – both consensus and minor variant analyses.
- d) Phylogenetic relationships among human and animal strains.
- e) Amino acid analyses – receptor binding sites, antigenic sites etc
Selected strains may be also used for downstream biological characterization (T2.2 & 2.3).

T2.2: In vitro and ex vivo biological characterization of SARS-CoV2. Assessment of in vitro systems for characterization of SARS-CoV-2 strains. Including live virus (infectious) recovery sensitivity and species specificity:

- a) Cell lines of species origin,
b) Virus Neutralisation Assays optimisation – wild type and pseudotypes

Ex vivo explants and air-liquid interphase cultures of several animal species will be infected with SARS-CoV-2:

- c) Ex vivo organ cultures,
d) Air liquid interface

Viruses replicating in these systems will be characterized with respect to genome analysis, viral growth and host responses

T2.3: Development, optimization and harmonization of animal models for SARS-CoV2 characterization. Animal models species type for veterinary health and animal models for human disease including zoonoses.

- a) Exchange of protocols and experimental designs (infection, transmission, therapeutic intervention etc)
b) Explore and share pathology parameters (virus, receptors etc).
c) Undertake host response and cellular biomarkers analyses – innate and adaptive (humoral and cellular).

T2.4: Analyses of virus traits related to zoonotic and/or reverse zoonotic transmission

Outcomes and materials from this WP tasks and other WPs will allow:

- a) Variant analyses on host species change progeny viruses
b) Host cell ACE2 receptor virus interaction analyses.
c) Antigenic site modifications determination including cartography.
d) A variant virus in vivo investigation.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D2.2.2	Report on assessment of VNA techniques and comparison with ELISA reactivity data.	M51
D2.3.2	Report on pathology per species and investigative toolboxes.	M51
D2.1.3	Report on the development of an algorithm for novel virus assessment.	M54
D2.4.1	Collated partner outcomes of virus trait change as a result of species change including cell receptor affinity	M54
D2.2.3	Report on complex culture viral characterisation.	M57
D2.4.2	Report on in silico and antigenic cartography analysis of antigenic site adaptation traits.	M57

D2.3.3	Report on virus-host interaction parameters across susceptible species.	M60
D2.4.3	Undertake and report on a virus variant in vivo follow-up study.	M60
<p>Objectives WP3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To integrate the currently fragmented data from sampling of animals and the environment (WP1) across partner countries, into an aligned One-Health surveillance system for SARS-CoV-2 • To combine aligned surveillance with the data on bioavailability in samples (WP1) to inform risk assessment and transmission models. • To use WP3 outcomes to provide evidence for decision makers and other stakeholders to understand the risk posed by potential animal hosts, the environment, or fomites in the transmission of SARS-CoV-2. 		
<p>Description of work</p> <p>WP: 3 SARS-CoV2 risk assessment and surveillance WP start month: 40 WP end month: 66 WP Leader: Joaquin Prada (UoS) WP Deputy: Mirjam Kretzschmar (RIVM) WP participants: ANSES (P1), Ages (P2), Sciensano (P4), VRI (P8), FLI (P10), INIA (P16), UCM (P17), APHA (P21), UoS (P23), ISS (27), IZSAM (P28), IZSLER (P29), RIVM (P30), WBVR (P31), NVI (P33), PIWET (P34), INIAV (P35), INSA (P36), SVA (P41).</p> <p>Short description of WP3: Integration of surveillance activities in wildlife, food producing animals, pets and the environment (incl. sewage). Mapping of surveillance data obtained from wildlife, food producing animals, pets and the environment (incl. sewage). Identifying risk factors for virus transmission in wildlife reservoirs, food producing animals and the environment. Establishing models for transmission routes and risk assessment in a One health perspective.</p> <p>T3.1: Integration of surveillance activities. Design of a format/procedure for sampling/surveillance data on wildlife, food producing animals, pets, and the environment, from partner institutes, suitable to inform risk assessment. Collection of sampling/surveillance data from partner institutes and integration in the common framework. Investigation to identify additional sources of data (existing and novel) across the partner countries, and integration into the common framework when possible.</p> <p>T3.2: Mapping of surveillance data Evaluation of current surveillance activities being carried out, particularly in the animal sector, and assessment of similarities and differences between member countries, as well as opportunities for alignment. Identification of key stakeholders at national level needed to be involved for a successful implementation of One Health surveillance activities across member states.</p> <p>T3.3: Risk factors for virus transmission Conduction of an epidemiological survey to analysis the transmission of SARS-CoV-2 in both heavily and normally exposed pets (i.e. healthcare personal households and "normal" households, respectively). Sampling both heavily and normally exposed pets. Diagnosis of infections with SARS-CoV-2 using PCR-ELISA. Identification of potential risk factors for pet-human transmission of SARS-CoV-2.</p>		

T3.4: Models for transmission routes and risk assessment in a One Health perspective
Overview of different dynamics models and required parameters to test hypotheses regarding the role of animals as potential reservoir hosts and parameters needs. Systematic review to collect data on transmissibility of SARS-CoV2 of different animal hosts. This review will mainly target published and grey experimental data. Expected outputs from this review are quantification of transmission parameters characterising direct contact and if possible indirect transmission (contribution of the environment, including survival data generate by WP1). Assess susceptibility of different animals hosts by assessing collected data on sampling of wildlife, livestock, pets, and systematic review of challenge and dose-response experiments. Data collection on the mink outbreaks and assessment of transmission: mink-to-mink, between mink farms and mink-to-humans.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D3.4.5	Report describing the transmission characteristics of the mink outbreaks for the countries where data was available.	M51
D3.1.2	Database on sampling on wildlife, food producing animals, pets, and the environment.	M54
D3.3.1	Report on epidemiological survey design and clinical data (including anamnesis and lab results).	M54
D3.4.2	Systematic review report and quantification of transmission parameters for different animal species.	M54
D3.1.3	Report on the investigation and possibilities of integration.	M57
D3.4.3	List of susceptible hosts and relative risk ranking of susceptibility	M60
D3.2.2	Report on key stakeholders across member countries and opportunities for alignment of One Health surveillance activities	M63
D3.3.2	Report on the epidemiological survey results and risk factor assessment for pet-human SARS-Cov-2 transmission.	M63
D3.4.4	Report on SR of challenge experiments using different host species	M63

Objectives WP4

- To study virus-host interactions of other coronaviruses to better understand which determinants are critical for infection of humans or susceptible animal species in particular (*Felidae, Mustelidae, Cricetidae* etc.)
- To identify possible molecular mechanisms of evolution and host adaptation by investigating adaptive potential of different relevant animal CoVs from different genera under natural and experimental conditions.
- To study the drivers of coronavirus emergence to enhance preparedness.
- To assess which coronaviruses have the greatest potential for cross-species interactions through study of genetic diversity and global scale phylodynamics
- To early identify zoonotic and reverse zoonotic adaptations in order to raise preparedness by highlighting ecological opportunities and human practices that have a direct impact on coronaviruses evolution in animals and in the vicinity of humans.
- To model coronavirus emergence risks in different virus-host interaction situations. Increased knowledge of the risk of virus emergence in specific situations will be very helpful for trying to control such risks.

Description of work

WP: 4 Coronavirus preparedness
WP start month: 40
WP end month: 66

WP Leader: (ANSES) (Nicolas Eterradossi)
 WP Deputy: WBVR (Wim van der Poel)
 WP participants: NSES (P1), VRI (P8), Bfr (P9), FLI (P10), APHA (P21), ISS (27), IZSAM (P28), IZSLER (P29), WBVR (P31), PIWET (P34), INIAV (P35); Associated expert CHU Caen

Short description of WP4:

Study of virus – host interactions, looking into virus evolution and host adaptation. Identifying drivers of virus emergence through evaluation of phylodynamics and cross-species interactions with focus on zoonotic and reverse zoonotic aspects and adaptations. Use of generated data and research outcomes for virus emergence risk modelling to improve surveillance and control strategies, intervention strategies and prevention.

T4.1: Virus-host interaction

- a) Inoculation studies using different coronaviruses (Besides beta-Coronaviruses, gamma-Coronaviruses like IBV, TCoV and GfCoV may be used) i.e. with a common genetic backbone but different S genes in SPF poultry. Viruses isolated from heterogenous host will be passaged.
- b) Recombination studies between coronaviruses of the same genus (for experimental models and different viruses – e.g. from wild rodents – in cell cultures or ex vivo) to assess frequency and strain specificity of these events.
- c) Isolation attempts of betacoronavirus detected in hedgehogs and other wildlife species to explore the possibility of a cross-species transmission to humans by using animal models of Covid-19 (i.e. hamsters and/or ferrets)

T4.2: Drivers of virus emergence

Analyses of genetic diversity and global scale phylodynamics of coronaviruses of domestic animals and wildlife.

- a) to reconstruct the phylodynamics of these viruses at global time and geographical scales, within and between both species and breeding facilities.
- b) to trace relevant virus mutations and recombination events
- c) to assess the impact of ecological factors (species interactions, habitat, etc) and human interventions (vaccination, trading of animals, etc.) on coronaviruses evolution (rates, composition of recombinants, potential contribution of vaccine strains) and spread (transmission chain between breeding facilities, detection of focal points or super spreaders).

Aim for a One Health approach for pandemic preparedness.

T4.3: Virus emergence risk modelling

Collecting data from specific animal communities over a pre-defined period of time:

- a) by high frequency sampling of bats and cats in a natural or domestic environment over a period of time
- b) by taking monthly fecal samples from cats and kittens housed under breeding farm conditions
- c) by frequent sampling of wildlife including hedgehogs hosted in animal health centres for several months and taking into account the results of tasks 4.1 and 4.2, the potential impact on other species incl. humans' will be inferred.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D4.2.2	Report on harmonized methods for coronavirus detection and metagenomic sequencing and detected coronavirus genomes.	M51
D4.1.1	Reports of in vivo and in vitro experimentations	M57
D4.3.1	Report on relevant sample types	M60
D4.1.2	Full-length genomes of viruses from a, b and c	M63

D4.2.3	Report of analyses of detected variations in Coronavirus sequences related to ecological factors and human interventions.	M63
D4.3.2	Report of pan coronavirus PCR screening, plus next generation sequencing of samples and viral diversity over time.	M63
D4.3.3	Report of coronavirus contaminations in wildlife species.	M63
D4.3.4	Risk assessment and modelling of coronavirus evolution	M63
Milestones		
Ref	Title	Due month
M4.1	In vitro and in vivo experiments performed	M54
M4.2	Samples collected under farming and natural conditions	M57
M4.3	Coronavirus evolution under experimental and natural conditions analyzed	M63
M4.4	impact on the capacity to cross the species barrier evaluated and risk modeled	M63

2.2.9.1.2 PhD03-R2-AMR2.1-HME-AMR

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)	AMR2.1: Dynamics of AMR selection, clonal spread and horizontal gene transfer in humans, animals and the environment, including epidemiology of resistant microorganisms and antimicrobials in the environment and their (environment-mediated) spread									
PhD Project Title	Investigating the role of heavy metals in the environment as a selective pressure for the dissemination of antimicrobial resistance									
PhD Project Acronym	HME-AMR									
PhD Supervising Organisation	P26-TEAGASC					Deputy PhD Supervising Organisation			P25-NUIG	
PhD Supervisor	Kaye Burgess					Deputy PhD Supervisor			Dearbháile Morris	
PhD Start month	M38					PhD End month			M74	
Annual period of the OHEJP the PhD work plan applies: Y6										
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BFR	FLI	RKI	DTU
PM										
Participant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRA	IP	APHA	PHE
PM										
Participant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	Wbvr	FHI
PM										
Participant	33	34	35	36	37	39	40	41	42	43
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	SLV	FOHM	SVA	NMVRVI	ISCIH
PM										
Participant	44	45	46	47						
	BIOR	RUOKA	THL	NEBIH						
PM										
Objectives										
- To characterise AMR Enterobacterales from agricultural soil of differing zinc concentrations										

- To characterise AMR Enterobacterales from bovine milk filter socks in regions differing zinc concentrations
- To characterise the resistome of agricultural soil of differing zinc concentrations
- To compare AMR isolates with those obtained from other sectors

Description of work

Selective pressures drive bacterial populations to evolve and may promote the dissemination of AMR genes, in the human and animal gut, or in the environment. However, there is limited information about the impact of selective pressures in the agri-food environment on HGT between microorganisms. One of the factors which can act as a selective pressure and can influence this HGT is the presence of heavy metals. Heavy metals occur ubiquitously in the agri-food environment and sometimes in high concentrations in soil. Very limited information is available regarding the impact of selective pressures such as heavy metals which may be present in the environment on the mobilisation of antimicrobial resistance and its potential transfer into the food chain. Within HME—AMR the presence of zinc is being investigated in relation to the presence and profile of antimicrobial resistance in the primary food production environment.

Following completion of the soil amendment study in Y5 (study 3 in the workplan) work in Y6 will focus on completing the analysis of soil samples (study 1) and bovine milk filters (study 2) collected from regions of high and low zinc concentration in Ireland. This will include phenotypic and genotypic characterisation of antimicrobial resistant Enterobacterales isolates obtained from the samples through culture based analysis and the characterisation of the resistome in the different areas by sequencing.

In the final study (study 4) the genomes of isolates obtained in studies 1, 2 and 3 will be compared with each other and relevant comparable isolates from different sources and geographic regions, obtained both from project partners and through public sequence repositories.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-PhD03-1.1	Report on AMR bacteria present in soils of differing heavy metal content	M69
D-PhD03-1.2	Report on the impact of the application of heavy metal containing amendments to AMR bacteria in soil	M60
D-PhD03-1.3	Report on AMR bacteria present in milk filters from animals grazing in areas of differing heavy metal content	M69

2.2.9.1.3 PhD04-R2-AMR2.1-KENTUCKY

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)	AMR 2.1: Dynamics of AMR selection, clonal spread and horizontal gene transfer in humans, animals and the environment, including epidemiology of resistant microorganisms and antimicrobials in the environment and their (environment-mediated) spread		
PhD Project Title	Exploring the evolutionary success of the antibiotic resistant Salmonella Kentucky ST198		
PhD Project Acronym	KENTUCKY		
PhD Supervisor	P4-Sciensano	Deputy PhD Supervising Organisation	P19-INRA

PhD Coordinator person name			Pieter-Jan Ceyskens		Deputy PhD Supervisor			Benoit Doublet		
PhD Start month			M30		PhD End month			M72		
Annual period of the OHEJP the PhD work plan applies: Y6										
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU
PM										
Participant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	NVNA	INRA	IP	APHA	PHE
PM										
Participant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	Wbvr	FHI
PM										
Participant	33	34	35	36	37	39	40	41	42	43
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	SLV	FOHMI	SVA	NMVRVI	ISCI
PM										
Participant	44	45	46	47						
	BIOR	RUOKA	THL	NEBIH						
PM										
<p>Objectives: <i>Salmonella enterica</i> serovar Kentucky (<i>S. Kentucky</i>) is a common causative agent of gastroenteritis in humans. It is one of most notorious <i>Salmonella</i> serotypes, as it is strongly associated with antimicrobial resistance (AMR). In this project, we will investigate (i) what explains the evolutionary success of the multidrug resistant <i>S. Kentucky</i> ST198 clone, (ii) what is the mechanisms of the integration (and potential further transfer) of the ESBL gene in its chromosome, and (iii) Are there genetic determinants of different human-animal host ranges in epidemic <i>S. Kentucky</i> ST198 and ST152?</p>										
<p>Description of work: In the last year of the PhD project (funded internally though Sciensano funding), the final focus will be applying the microfluidic platform which was established in Y5 and which we use to track- in real-time- the transfer of double parS labeled plasmid (R27 [ΔhtdA::frt-Cm-frt- pMTparS -ISEcp1-P1parS-</p>										

blaCTX-M-14b) from a donor *S. enterica* cell (MA8058 ΔpSLT; Δhns) to a recipient cell (MA8058 ΔpSLT Δara::tetR-Km-CFP:P1parB-YGFP:pMTparB), to broadly investigate transfer dynamics and the characterization of phenotypes related to metabolism and resistance.
With these results, we expect to establish an unparalleled insights into the physiological impact of prophages and plasmids in virulence and resistance of one of the most notorious *S. enterica* serotypes currently circulating on the European continent.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D6	Paper 2 (Tentative title). Transcriptome profile of clinical <i>S. Kentucky</i> strains	M72
D7	Paper 3 (Tentative title). The influence of Mobile Genetic Elements of the evolutionary success of the MDR <i>S. Kentucky</i> ST198 lineage	M72
D8	PhD Dissertation	M70

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
M5	All selected MGEs transferred to prophage- and plasmid-cured <i>S. enterica</i> host strain	M68
M6	PhD Defense	M72

2.2.9.1.4 PhD05-R2-AMR2/6.1/ET5-METAPRO

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)	AMR 2: Epidemiological studies into the dynamics of AMR in human and animal populations and the environment including horizontal gene transfer and selection of AMR AMR 6.1: Development of NGS-based tools for surveillance of AMR in Enterobacteriaceae in animals, humans and the environment ET 5: Ecology of emerging pathogens									
PhD Project Title	Metagenomics and genomic approaches for the prevention of the spread of plazomicin resistance in humans, animals and the environment									
PhD Project Acronym	METAPRO									
PhD Supervising Organisation	P17-UCM	Deputy PhD Supervising Organisation	P23-UoS							
PhD Supervisor	Bruno Gonzalez Zorn	Deputy PhD Supervisor	Roberto La Ragione							
PhD Start month	M27	PhD End month	M66							
Annual period of the OHEJP the PhD work plan applies: Y6										
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU
PM										
Participant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22

	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRA	IP	APHA	PHE
PM										
Participant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	Wbvr	FHI
PM										
Participant	33	34	35	36	37	39	40	41	42	43
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	SLV	FOHM	SVA	NMVRVI	ISCIH
PM										
Participant	44	45	46	47						
	BIOR	RUOKA	THL	NEBIH						
PM										

Objectives:

- Finish the last analyses of all the experiments performed during the Doctoral Project
- Thesis writing and defence

Description of work:

The last part of the analysis of all the experiments will be performed. When that part is finished, the thesis manuscript will be written, followed by the thesis defence.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D3	Thesis manuscript	M63
Ref	Title	Due month
M11	Thesis manuscript	M63
M12	Thesis defence	M66

2.2.9.1.5 PhD07-R2-ET2.1-MACE

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)	ET 2.1: Evaluation of early detection methods for emerging threats		
PhD Project Title	Mathematical models and economic evaluation for cystic echinococcosis control and elimination		
PhD Project Acronym	MACE		
PhD Supervising Organisation	P23-UoS	Deputy PhD Supervising Organisation	P27-ISS

PhD Supervisor			Joaquin Prada			Deputy PhD Supervisor			Adriano Casulli	
PhD Start month			M25			PhD End month			M63	
Annual period of the OHEJP the PhD work plan applies: Y6 - 2023										
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BFR	FLI	RKI	DTU
PM										
Participant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRA	IP	APHA	PHE
PM										
Participant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	Uos	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RVM	Wbvr	FHI
PM										
Participant	33	34	35	36	37	39	40	41	42	43
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	SLV	FOHMI	SVA	NMVRVI	ISCI
PM										
Participant	44	45	46	47						
	BIOR	RUOKA	THL	NEBIH						
PM										
Objectives										
2) Assess the most plausible and feasible CE control and elimination scenarios										
Description of work:										
The quantification of risk using geostatistical models will be formally inputted with our economic evaluations and transmission models, for a country in South America (i.e. Argentina) and in Europe (i.e. Italy). This step will integrate our different efforts (mathematical models, economic evaluation, and risk preference elicitation) to inform the true effectiveness of interventions.										
Deliverables										
Ref	Title									Due month
MACE.Y5.1	Final draft on economic analysis									M63
MACE.Y5.3	CE model integrating surveillance, control, economic evaluation and risk preference									M63

MACE.Y5.4	Final report to stakeholders	M63
Milestones		
Ref	Title	Due month

2.2.9.1.6 PhD08-R2-ET5.1/4.1/FBZSH3-DESIRE

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)	ET 5.1: The role of wildlife in the ecology of potentially zoonotic emerging threats ET 4.1: Host factors associated with increased susceptibility to infection and disease of emerging threats with undefined routes of transmission FBZ-SH 3: Source attribution of bacterial foodborne zoonoses and antimicrobial resistance considering also the environment and non-livestock reservoirs (e.g. pets and wildlife) as sources									
PhD Project Title	Developing Evidence-based Surveillance for emerging Rat-borne zoonoses in changing Environments									
PhD Project Acronym	DESIRE (Developing Evidence-based Surveillance for emerging Rat-borne zoonoses in changing Environments)									
PhD Supervising Organisation	P30-RIVM		Deputy PhD Supervising Organisation			P31-Wbvr				
PhD Supervisor	Miriam Maas		Deputy PhD Supervisor			Wim van der Poel				
PhD Start month	M22		PhD End month			M69				
Annual period of the OHEJP the PhD work plan applies: Y6 – 2023										
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Agés	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU
PM								>1		
Participant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRA	IP	APHA	PHE
PM										
Participant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	Wbvr	FHI
PM										
Participant	33	34	35	36	37	39	40	41	42	43

	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	SLV	FOHMI	SVA	NMVRMI	ISCIH
PM										
Participant	44	45	46	47						
	BIOR	RUOKA	THL	NEBIH						
PM										

Objectives

In the final year of the PhD, the analyses of the data that have been collected with the field study on the distribution of rat populations in various urban habitats and on the pathogens of rats will be finalized. Also the systematic literature reviews on pathogens of urban wildlife species will be combined in 1 review paper discussing the public health risks of urban wildlife.

If times allows, the population genetics data will be analysed, as well as the data on pathogens in urban mice.

Description of work:

1) the analyses of the data that has been collected with the field study on the distribution of rat populations in various urban habitats and on the pathogens of rats will be finalized and results will be written in two papers. These were due earlier (D2 and D5), but due to the extended field study, the delivery data was shifted.

2) By combining the insights from both papers, a policy advice on urban greening will be written.

3) the systematic literature reviews on pathogens of urban wildlife species will be combined in 1 review paper discussing the public health risks of urban wildlife.

The PhD candidate will join the Wageningen University International graduate school for Animal Sciences (WIAS) for courses and training.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D1	A PhD-thesis on evidence-based improvements of the surveillance of rat-borne zoonoses in changing environments.	September (M69)
D2	An international, peer reviewed publication about urban characteristics and the effect of city greening on rat populations	November (M59)
D5	An international, peer reviewed publication about urban characteristics and the effect of city greening on rat pathogens and related public health risks.	January (M61)
D4	An international, peer reviewed publication describing the public health risks of urban wildlife based on systematic literature reviews of these species	May(M63)
D6	A policy advice on rat-borne disease risks with regards to urban planning and the current trend of greener and bluer cities.	June (M66)
D7	Oral or poster presentation on a One Health conference	September (M68)

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
M4	Training and Education Statement of the WIAS	September(M69)

2.2.9.1.7 PhD09-R2-FBZSH3/AMR2.1-UDOFRIC

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)		<p>FBZ-SH 3: Source attribution of bacterial foodborne zoonoses and antimicrobial resistance also considering the environment and non-livestock reservoirs (e.g. pets and wildlife) as sources.</p> <p>AMR2.1: Dynamics of AMR selection, clonal spread and horizontal gene transfer in humans, animals and the environment, including epidemiology of resistant microorganisms and antimicrobials in the environment and their (environment-mediated) spread</p>								
PhD Project Title		Understanding the development of fluoroquinolone (FQ) resistance in <i>Campylobacter</i> present in broilers and the risks of FQ resistance persisting through the food-chain to cause disease in people								
PhD Project Acronym		UDoFRiC								
PhD Supervising Organisation		P21-APHA			Deputy PhD Supervising Organisation			P1-ANSES		
PhD Supervisor		John Rodgers			Deputy PhD Supervisor			Isabelle Kempf/Katell Rivoal		
PhD Start month		M27			PhD End month			M62		
Annual period of the OHEJP the PhD work plan applies: Y6 - 2023										
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU
PM										
Participant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRA	IP	APHA	PHE
PM										
Participant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	WbVR	FHI
PM										
Participant	33	34	35	36	37	39	40	41	42	43
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	SLV	FOHM	SVA	NMVRVI	ISCI

PM										
Participant	44	45	46	47						
	BIOR	RUOKA	THL	NEBIH						
PM										

Objectives

This project will exploit archives of *Campylobacter* and associated information (phenotypic, genomic, epidemiological meta-data) from surveillance and research across the food-chain to investigate the development and diversity of FQ resistance. The study will assess *in vitro* and *in vivo* biological fitness costs/benefits of resistance and determine if any specific FQ resistance variants found in poultry are more or less likely to persist and cause disease in people. Genomic analysis approaches, such as whole genome sequencing, will be used alongside microbiological and epidemiological methods in this project.

Description of work

Characterisation of historic surveillance data. Student has collated and updated historic surveillance data from the national surveillance archives and identified data gaps. The student has updated these data gaps and brought all data in line with experimental techniques such as whole genome sequencing (WGS) and minimal inhibition concentration assays (MIC). All data has been brought together work is to be carried out to best describe temporal trends in the data and identify any common factors associated with FQ resistance.

Whole genome sequencing (WGS) and bioinformatics training. The student has completed training WGS and bioinformatics and can identify genes associated with resistance and the effect that resistance has upon the overall fitness and persistence throughout the food chain of *Campylobacter*. Isolates from key periods of time in the history of FQ use have been selected from the database that spans back over 25 years.

In vivo and in vitro studies. From September 2021 until September 2022 the student was carrying out work at ANSES in France including *in vitro* and *in vivo* fitness studies. *In vitro* studies included measuring the growth kinetics of susceptible strains and their fluoroquinolone resistant isogenic mutants and the survival capabilities of these strains in different conditions. *In vivo* were carried out to understand the competitive colonisation potential of our strains and their fluoroquinolone resistant isogenic mutants in specific pathogen free leghorn chickens.

Other training and development. Throughout the PhD there will be opportunities for numerous presentations and conference attendance (One Health EJP annual scientific conference Warwick Medical school post graduate symposium and the international society for animal hygiene (ISAH) 2022 conference in Berlin) to develop skills and understand the impact of the study in the context of the broader scientific community.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-PhD09-2.2	Report on the relationship between WGS and phenotype.	M63
D-PhD09-3.1	In vivo selection and characterization of isogenic resistant strains	M62
D-PhD09-3.4	In vivo study: comparison of colonisation using chicken models	M66

2.2.9.1.8 PhD10-R2-FBZSH3/AMR2.1-WILBR

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)		FBZ-SH 3: Source attribution of bacterial foodborne zoonoses and antimicrobial resistance. AMR 2.1: Dynamics of AMR selection, clonal spread and horizontal gene transfer.								
PhD Project Title		Contribution of wild birds to AMR in the environment and on farm.								
PhD Project Acronym		WILBR								
PhD Supervising Organisation		P21-APHA			Deputy PhD Supervising Organisation			P41-SVA		
PhD Supervisor		Muna Anjum			Deputy PhD Supervisor			Stefan Borjesson		
PhD Start month		M21			PhD End month			M67		
Annual period of the OHEJP the PhD work plan applies - Y6-2023										
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BFR	FLI	RKI	DTU
PM										
Participant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRA	IP	APHA	PHE
PM										
Participant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RVM	wbvr	FHI
PM										
Participant	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	IC	SLV	FOHM	SVA	
PM										
Objectives for Y3 of PhD:										
<p>1) Collection of microbiological samples for longitudinal study Collection of faecal samples from pigs and gulls will provide insight into each species microbiome as we can isolate bacteria from the samples and carry out phenotypic and genotypic testing to identify levels of AMR in the populations.</p> <p>2) Molecular analysis of bacterial isolates and antimicrobial resistance Molecular analysis of isolates will allow bacterial species to be identified and any resistance profiles to be established. Comparisons can then be drawn between isolates from pigs, and isolates from gulls.</p> <p>3) Characterisation of mobile elements transmitting/proliferating AMR.</p>										

Further characterisation will make it possible to identify if any of the antimicrobial resistance genes are mobile, and if so which mobile genetic elements (MGE) they are located on. Carrying out this analysis on pig and gull isolates would allow us to see if any MGEs are being found in both populations, inferring a transfer of resistance.

Description of work:

1) Collection of microbiological samples for longitudinal study

The farms successfully recruited for the longitudinal study will be visited twice and an as of yet undecided number of pig faecal samples will be collected. In collaboration with the wildlife team based at Sand Hutton (York) gull faeces will be identified from the environment and collected.

2) Molecular analysis of bacterial isolates and antimicrobial resistance.

Enterobacteriaceae will be isolated from faecal samples collected using selective media. Isolates will undergo short-read sequencing and analysed using several bioinformatics programmes and pipelines to identify species and the presence of AMR determinants.

3) Characterisation of mobile elements transmitting/proliferating AMR.

Further bioinformatics analysis will help identify any MGEs. Long-read sequencing of any isolates harbouring resistance to critically important antibiotics on MGEs or multi-drug resistant MGEs can undergo long-read sequencing in order to circularise any plasmids.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
1	Completion of 9 month review	M57
2	Completion of 12 month review	M60

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
1	Collection of microbiological samples for longitudinal study	M56
2	Molecular analysis of bacterial isolates and antimicrobial resistance	M60
3	Characterisation of mobile elements transmitting/proliferating AMR	M60
4	Completion of 9 month review	M57
5	Completion of 12 month review	M60

2.2.9.1.9 PhD11-R1-FBZ4/5- EnvDis

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)	FBZ 4: Source attribution and transmission routes FBZ 5: Epidemiological studies: risk factors and dynamics									
PhD Project Title	Environment and Foodborne Zoonosis: Linking Mechanism and Phenomenology									
PhD Project Acronym	EnvDis									
PhD Supervising Organisation	P23-UoS	Deputy PhD Supervising Organisation	P23-UoS							
PhD Supervisor	Giovanni (Gianni) Lo Iacono	Deputy PhD Supervisor	Alasdair (Alex) Cook							
PhD Start month	M25	Project End month	M63							
Annual period of the OHEJP the PhD work plan applies: Y6 – 2023										
	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12

Partici pant	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BFR	FLI	RKI	DTU
PM										
Partici pant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
Partici pant	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRA	IP	APHA	PHE
PM										
Partici pant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
Partici pant	Uos	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RVM	WBVR	FHI
PM										
Partici pant	33	34	35	36	37	39	40	41	42	43
Partici pant	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	SLV	FOHM	SVA	NMVRVI	ISCIII
PM										
Partici pant	44	45	46	47						
Partici pant	BIOR	RUOKA	THL	NEBIH						
PM										

Objectives

- 01.** Can we identify and access “big data” – existing information that can be interrogated to yield new evidence for decision-making in One Health? The generation of new analytical approaches would provide tools that could then be adapted to specific animal or human health issues where environment plays a key role in aetiology.
- 02.** Can we identify the key environmental processes triggering and propagating zoonoses?
- 03.** Can we disentangle the role of animal, human (including socio-economic factors) and environmental factors in zoonoses?
- 04.** Can we identify the delay between variations in the environment (e.g. increase in the temperature or behavioural change) and the occurrence of a foodborne outbreak?
- 05.** How can we quantify their impact on Animal and Public Health?

Description of work

WP1

WP start month: January 2020 (25M)

WP end month: December 2022 (60M)

WP Leader Gianni Lo Iacono

Deputy WP Leader: Alex Cook

WP participants-PhD Student: Laura Gonzalez Villeta

Description of the WP:

To develop a general tool to assess the risk of infectious diseases (in particular zoonosis) when we have information of relevant environmental factors.

T-1-1: Test and discuss findings of the model for salmonellosis; validate the model with data from another European country; include animal role in the model from available data; write up thesis.

Task start month: 25M

Task end month: 60M

Task Leader: Gianni Lo Iacono

Deputy Task Leader: Alex Cook

Task Participants: Laura Gonzalez Villeta, Alex Cook, Gianni Lo Iacono

Description of the task: Laura will get the data for England and Wales from collaborators at PHE, the environmental data from the MetOffice and Copernicus, animal data from Defra and APHA, previous laboratory findings to build up the model from the literature and salmonellosis data from another European country willing to collaborate, potentially under a OHEJP STM.

sT-1-1.1: Test and discuss findings of the model for salmonellosis

Sub-Task start month: 37M

Sub-Task end month: 48M

Sub-Task Leader: Gianni Lo Iacono

Deputy Task Leader: Alex Cook

Task Participants: Laura Gonzalez Villeta, Alex Cook, Gianni Lo Iacono

sT-1-1.2: Validate the model with data from another European country; include animal role in the model from (if) available data

Sub-Task start month: 49M

Sub-Task end month: 54M

Sub-Task Leader: Gianni Lo Iacono

Deputy Task Leader: Alex Cook

Task Participants: Laura Gonzalez Villeta, Alex Cook, Gianni Lo Iacono

sT-1-1.3: Write up thesis

Sub-Task start month: 55M

Sub-Task end month: 60M

Sub-Task Leader: Gianni Lo Iacono

Deputy Task Leader: Alex Cook

Task Participants: Laura Gonzalez Villeta

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-PhD11-1.1	Presentation of findings (e.g. conferences, internal school seminars)	M36
D-PhD11-1.2	End of Year Confirmation Report	M36
D-PhD11-1.3	Completion/Submission of thesis	M63

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
M-PhD11-1	Test and discuss findings of the model for Salmonellosis	M48
M-PhD11-2	Validate the model with data from another European country	M55
M-PhD11-3	Write up thesis	M60
M-PhD11-3	Completion/Submission of thesis	M63

2.2.9.1.10 Phd13-R2-FBZ8/AMR2-VIMOGUT-AMR

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)		FBZ 8: Model Systems (in vitro and in vivo) to study host/food – microbe interactions AMR 2: Epidemiological studies into the dynamics of AMR in human and animals populations and the environment including horizontal gene transfer and selection of AMR								
PhD Project Title		<i>In Vitro</i> and <i>in Vivo</i> analyses and MODulation of the chicken GUT microbiome to combat AMR.								
PhD Project Acronym		VIMOGUT-AMR								
PhD Supervising Organisation		P31-WbvR			Deputy PhD Supervising Organisation			P21-APHA		
PhD Supervisor		Michael Brouwer			Deputy PhD Supervisor			Muna Anjum		
PhD Start month		M20			PhD End month			M68		
Annual period of the OHEJP the PhD work plan applies: Y6 - 2023										
Participating	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BFR	FLI	RKI	DTU
PM										
Participating	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRA	IP	APHA	PHE
PM										
Participating	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	WBvR	FHI
PM									9,76	
Participating	33	34	35	36	37	39	40	41	42	43
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	SLV	FOHM	SVA	NMVRVI	ISCI
PM										
Participating	44	45	46	47						
	BIOR	RUOKA	THL	NEBIH						

PM									
Objectives									
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carry out experiments in the <i>in vitro</i> model to test ESBL <i>E. coli</i> colonisation intervention strategies. • Carry out experiments in the <i>in vitro</i> model to test the transfer range of ESBL plasmids within the microbiome. • Carry out experiments in the <i>in vitro</i> model to test ESBL <i>E. coli</i> conjugation intervention strategies. • Finish all laboratory wet work before the end of this year. 									
Description of work									
<p>Due to COVID-19, sample collection on farm was delayed and is now planned at the end of Y4. Deliverable 2 and Milestones 8 and 9 have been postponed to Y5. As such, Milestones 12 and 13 and deliverable 3 will be postponed to Y6.</p> <p>The microbiome analysis of caecal samples will be performed, analysed and written into a manuscript, describing more in-depth how the relationship is between the developing chicken gut microbiome and colonisation by ESBL <i>E. coli</i>. Samples that were collected from different broiler farms and flocks during VIMOGUT-AMR in year 4 are analysed.</p> <p>Laboratory wet work for the project will focus on the use of the <i>in vitro</i> chicken gut model in three areas, continuing from the results that are generated during year 4.</p> <p>Experiments focussing on intervention strategies to prevent ESBL <i>E. coli</i> colonisation in the chicken gut model will be tested.</p> <p>A STM proposal to create fluorescently labelled plasmids has been submitted and, if granted, these will be made at the University of Copenhagen. Experiments to determine the transfer of ESBL plasmids from <i>E. coli</i> through the <i>in vitro</i> gut microbiome will be carried out using these plasmids.</p> <p>Finally, based on the strategies from the literature study in year 3, strategies for intervention of plasmid transfer within the microbiome will be tested.</p>									
Deliverables									
Ref	Title							Due month	
D2	Manuscript on relationship between chicken gut microbiome maturation and ESBL colonisation over several farms.							56	
D3	Manuscript describing the results of the results of testing <i>in vitro</i> ESBL <i>E. coli</i> intervention strategies.							68	
Milestones									
Ref	Title							Due month	
M8	Perform 16S sequencing and analysis of caecal samples from OH-EJP VIMOGUT.							50	
M9	Write manuscript on relationship between chicken gut microbiome maturation and ESBL colonisation over several farms.							56	
M10	Experiments in the <i>in vitro</i> model for ESBL <i>E. coli</i> colonisation intervention strategies.							60	
M11	Experiments in the <i>in vitro</i> model to test the transfer range of ESBL plasmids within the microbiome.							60	
M12	Experiments in the <i>in vitro</i> model to test ESBL plasmid conjugation intervention strategies.							64	
M13	Write the manuscript describing the results of the results of testing <i>in vitro</i> ESBL <i>E. coli</i> intervention strategies.							68	

2.2.9.1.11 PhD15-R2-FBZ5-TRACE

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)		FBZ 5: Epidemiological studies: risk factors and dynamics								
PhD Project Title		Tracking the public health hazard of foodborne Hepatitis E								
PhD Project Acronym		TRACE (TRacking public health risk of hepatitisE)								
PhD Supervising Organisation		P30-RIVM			Deputy PhD Supervising Organisation			P31-Wbvr		
PhD Supervisor		Eelco Franz			Deputy PhD Supervisor			Wim van der Poel		
PhD Start month		M21			PhD End month			M66		
Annual period of the OHEJP the PhD work plan applies: Y6-2023										
Participating	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BFR	FLI	RKI	DTU
PM										
Participating	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRA	IP	APHA	PHE
PM										
Participating	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAMI	IZSLER	RIVM	Wbvr	FHI
PM										
Participating	33	34	35	36	37	39	40	41	42	43
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	SLV	FOHM	SVA	NMVRVI	ISCIH
PM										
Participating	44	45	46	47						
	BIOR	RUOKA	THL	NEBIH						
PM										
Objectives										

<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. on explaining HEV strain shifts and HEV disease outcomes related to HEV circulation and HEV variability 2. Evaluation of results for future anticipation and intervention as possible. 		
Description of work Bioinformatics data generated and analyzed in WP1 and WP 2 will be evaluated in association with the results from WP3. It is envisaged that evaluations will help to explain and predict HEV dynamics and thereby help public and veterinary health to anticipate on the changing epidemiology of HEV.		
Deliverables		
Ref	Title	Due month
D3	Identification of virulence genes and elucidation of the relationship between quasispecies and changing virulence of circulating HEV strains	64
D4	Report explaining HEV strain shifts and HEV disease outcomes related to HEV circulation and HEV variability. Evaluation of results for future anticipation and intervention as possible.	64
D5	Evaluation of results for future anticipation and intervention as possible.	64
Milestones		
Ref	Title	Due month
N/A		

2.2.9.2 List of programmed activities

Activity	Lead beneficiary	PM	Start Month	End Month
WP1	1-Anses	82.06	61	69
WP2	30-RIVM	1.5	61	69
WP3	4-Sciensano	16.58	61	69
WP4	41-SVA	11.63	61	69
WP5	9-BfR	18.5	61	69
WP6	23-UoS	13.6	61	69
WP7	27-ISS	4	61	69
JIP06-COVRIN	31-WbvR	29.64	61	63

2.2.9.3 Annual Deliverables List

Deliverable N°	Deliverable Title	WP N°	Lead beneficiary	Due Date (in Month)
D1.19	Annual report on the internal and external newsletter produced during the fifth and sixth year	WP1	1 - ANSES	69
D1.20	Complete version of annual and final reports for stakeholders n°5	WP1	1 - ANSES	67
D1.21	Submit report on sustainability of website	WP1	1 - ANSES	69
D1.22	Submit a special issue on One Health to a relevant journal	WP1	1 - ANSES	66
D1.31	Summary Progress Report Y6	WP1	1 - ANSES	69
D3.20	Final reports of 2nd call JRPs and evaluation reports	WP3	4 - SCIENSANO	65
D3.21	5th periodic report on JRPs	WP3	4 - SCIENSANO	63
D4.28	Final report of 2nd call JIPs and evaluation reports on evaluation of finalised JIPs, 2nd round	WP4	41 - SVA	65
D4.29	5th periodic report on JIPs	WP4	41 - SVA	63
D4.30	Report on the OHEJP exercise SimEx	WP4	41 - SVA	63
D4.31	Final report of JIP COVRIN and evaluation report	WP4	41 - SVA	66
D5.11	Report on a stakeholder conference	WP5	9 - BFR	68
D6.13	Report of the third CPD module in one health	WP6	23 - UoS	62
D6.14	Report n°3 of the annual short term missions completed also uploaded onto the EJP webpage.	WP6	23 - UoS	62 (submitted in M54)

Deliverable N°	Deliverable Title	WP N°	Lead beneficiary	Due Date (in Month)
D6.15	Report on outputs of the short term missions	WP6	23 - UoS	62
D6.18	Thesis Reports of up to 17 PhD studentships	WP6	23 - UoS	66
D6.20	Report n°4 of the annual short term missions completed also uploaded onto the EJP webpage.	WP6	23 - UoS	62

2.3 Participation in Annual Work Plan activities

Beneficiaries concerned : P01-ANSES, P02-AGES, P04-SCIENSANO, P06-NDRVMI, P07-SZU, P08-VRI, P09-BfR, P10-FLI, P11-RKI, P12-DTU, P13-SSI, P14-UTARTU, P15-VFL, P16-INIA, P17-UCM, P18-MVNA, P19-INRAE P20-IP, P22-PHE, P23-UoS, P24-NNK, P25-NUIG, P26-TEAGASC, P27-ISS, P28-IZSAM, P29-IZSLER, P30-RIVM, P32-FHI, P33-NVI, P34-PIWET, P35-INIAV, P36-INSA, P37-IISPV, P39-SLV, P40-FoHM, 42-NMVRVI, 43-ISCIII44, -BIOR, 45-RUOKA, 46-THL, 47-NEBIH	
Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be subcontracted) (article 13 of MGA)	N
Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by linked third parties (article 14 of MGA)	N
Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 11 and 12 of MGA)	N
Does the participant envisage the provision of financial support to third parties (article 15 of MGA)	N

2.3.1 P21-APHA

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be subcontracted) (article 13 of MGA)	N
Does the participant envisage that part of its work will be performed by linked third parties (article 14 of MGA)	N
Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contributions provided by third parties (articles 11 and 12 of MGA)	Y
<p>WP6 / Task 6.4 Doctoral Training Programme: APHA is not an academic institution and as such is not in position to hire PhD student. Consequently, APFA will use Article 11 of the GA to support the following PhDs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Activity PhD09-R2-FBZSH3/AMR2.1-UDOFRIC: APHA will use the services provided by a PhD student to carry out PhD09- UDOFRIC activities in APHA premises. This PhD student will be employed and paid by the University of Warwick. This person will therefore be a seconded employee paid by University of Warwick and working for APHA. His salary will be supported by the OHEJP under Article 11: in-kind contribution provided by third parties against payment. The work will be carried out on beneficiary's premises. Activity PhD10-R2-FBZSH3/AMR2.1-WILBR: APHA will use the services provided by a PhD student to carry out PhD10-WILBR activities in APHA premises. This PhD student will be employed and paid by the University of Exeter. This person will therefore be a seconded employee paid by University of Exeter and working for APHA. His salary will be supported by the OHEJP under Article 11: in-kind contribution provided by third parties against payment. The work will be carried out on beneficiary's premises. 	
Does the participant envisage the provision of financial support to third parties (article 15 of MGA)	N

2.3.2 P31-WbVR

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be subcontracted) (article 13 of MGA)	N
Does the participant envisage that part of its work will be performed by linked third parties (article 14 of MGA)	N

Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contributions provided by third parties (articles 11 and 12 of MGA)	Y
<p>WP6 / Task 6.4 Doctoral Training Programme: WbVR will use in-kind contribution for the following activity under Article 11:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activity PhD13-R2-FBZ8/AMR2-VIMOGUT-AMR: WbVR will use the services provided by a PhD student to carry out PhD13 WIMOGUT-AMR activities in WbVR premises. This PhD student will be employed and paid by the Wageningen University & Research (WUR). This person will therefore be a seconded employee paid by WUR and working for WbVR. His salary will be supported by the OHEJP under Article 11 of the GA: in-kind contribution provided by third parties against payment. <p>The work will be carried out on beneficiary's premises</p>	
Does the participant envisage the provision of financial support to third parties (article 15 of MGA)	N

2.3.3 P41-SVA

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be subcontracted) (article 13 of MGA)	N
Does the participant envisage that part of its work will be performed by linked third parties (article 14 of MGA)	N
Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contributions provided by third parties (articles 11 and 12 of MGA)	Y
<p>WP7/ T7.4: Making the bridges between EJP's beneficiaries and stakeholders sustainable SVA will use Article 11 of the GA to carry out the T7.4: Making the bridges between EJP's beneficiaries and stakeholders sustainable. The task of drafting of a detailed plan for an EU-wide analysis of current work processes, shared infrastructures, reference documents and guidelines across the multifaceted OH interface (environmental health-animal health-public health) will be conducted partly in the form of a PhD project in collaboration with Roskilde University (DK), Department of Social Sciences and Business. The contribution from Roskilde University will be to cover a part of PhD salary and tuition fees. The work will be carried out on Roskilde University's premises. In-kind contributions not used on beneficiary's premises.</p>	
Does the participant envisage the provision of financial support to third parties (article 15 of MGA)	N

2.4 Resources to be committed

2.4.1 Summary Effort Table

2.4.1.1 Overarching activities

Organisation	WP1- Coordination	WP2-SRA	WP3-JRPs management	WP4-JIPs management	WP5- Science to Policy translation	WP6-T&E management	WP7- Sustainability	Total
P01-Anses	43,08							43,08
P02-Ages	0,00							0,00
P04-Sciensano	4,58		15,58	1,13				21,29
P06-NDRVMI	0,00							0,00
P07-SZU	0,00							0,00
P08-VRI	0,00							0,00
P09-BfR	0,00				11,00			11,00
P10-FLI	0,00							0,00
P11-RKI	0,00							0,00
P12-DTU	0,00							0,00
P13-SSI	0,00		1,00		7,50			8,50
P14-UT	0,00							0,00
P15-VFL	0,00							0,00
P16-INIA	0,00							0,00
P17-UCM	0,00	0,75						0,75
P18-MVNA	0,00							0,00
P19-INRAE	0,00							0,00
P20-IP	0,00							0,00
P21-APHA	0,00							0,00

Annual Work Plan
Sixth Year – 2023
M61-M69

Organisation	WP1-Coordination	WP2-SRA	WP3-JRPs management	WP4-JIPs management	WP5-Science to Policy translation	WP6-T&E management	WP7-Sustainability	Total
P22-PHE	0,00							0,00
P23-UoS	34,40					12,40		46,80
P24-NNK	0,00							0,00
P25-NUIG	0,00							0,00
P26-TEAGASC	0,00							0,00
P27-ISS	0,00						2,00	2,00
P28-IZS AM	0,00							0,00
P29-IZS LER	0,00							0,00
P30-RIVM	0,00	0,75						0,75
P31-WbvR	0,00					1,20		1,20
P32-FHI	0,00							0,00
P33-NVI	0,00							0,00
P34-PIWET	0,00							0,00
P35-INIAV	0,00							0,00
P36-INSA	0,00			1,50				1,50
P37-IISPV	0,00							0,00
P39-SLV	0,00							0,00
P40-FoHM	0,00							0,00
P41-SVA	0,00			9,00			2,00	11,00
P42-NMVRVI	0,00							0,00
P43-ISCI	0							0
P44-BIOR	0							0
P45-RUOKA	0							0
P46-THL	0							0
P47-NEBIH	0							0
TOTAL	82,06	1,5	16,58	11,63	18,5	13,6	4	147,87

2.4.1.2 Joint Integrative Project

Organisation	JIP06-Covrin	TOTAL
P01-Anses	8,90	8,90
P02-Ages	0,00	0,00
P04-Sciensano	0,10	0,10
P08-VRI	0,00	0,00
P09-BfR	0,60	0,60
P10-FLI	5,67	5,67
P16-INIA	1,00	1,00
P17-UCM	0,25	0,25
P21-APHA	2,80	2,80
P23-UoS	1,89	1,89
P27-ISS	0,75	0,75
P28-IZS AM	0,90	0,90
P29-IZS LER	0,17	0,17
P30-RIVM	1,83	1,83
P31-WbvR	0,70	0,70
P33-NVI	1,60	1,60
P34-PIWET	1,86	1,86
P35-INIAV	0,60	0,60
P36-INSA	0,29	0,29
P41-SVA	0,77	0,77
P44-BIOR	0,40	0,40
Total	31,08	31,08

2.4.2 Other major cost items (equipment, goods and services, travel & subsistence, meetings organisation)

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
P01-Anses	0,00		13580		8800		15000	
WP1	0,00		7080		5500		15000	
WP1-Coordination	0,00		7080	CFS costs	5500	1 SSB meeting - 1 Stakeholder conference meeting	15000	1 Final meeting
WP4	0,00		6500		3300		0	
JIP06-COVID19-COVRIN	0,00		6500	Scientific publication LHN - Samples transport LHN- Laboratory reagents & consumables LRFSN (tips, syringes, culture flasks, tubes, eppendorfs)	3300	Various meetings for WP1, 2, 3 and 4 tasks	0	
P02-Ages	0,00		8000		2500		12868,3	
WP1	0,00		8000		2500		12868,3	
WP1-Coordination	0,00		8000	CFS costs	2500	1 Final stakeholder conference meeting - 1 Final meeting	12868,3	1 SSB meeting
P04-Sciensano	0,00		19112		7500		0	
WP1	0,00		9500		7500		0	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
WP1-Coordination	0,00		9500	Ethic reviewers - CFS costs	7500	1 SSB meeting - 1 Stakeholder conference meeting - 1 Final meeting	0	
WP3	0,00		9000		0		0	
WP3-JRPs management	0,00		9000	JRP/JIP external reviewers for 18 JRPs/JIPs reviews	0		0	
WP4	0,00		612		0		0	
WP4-JIPs management	0,00		0		0		0	
JIP06 COVRIN	0,00		612	IndiMag Pathogen Kit - AgPath-ID™ One-Step RT-PCR Reagents - reagents for molecular biology and sequencing - Innate immunity - digital PCR - kit	0		0	
P06-NDRVMI	0,00		0		2500		0	
WP1	0,00		0		2500		0	
WP1-Coordination	0,00		0		2500	1 SSB meeting - 1 Stakeholder conference meeting - 1 Final meeting	0	
P07-SZU	0,00		0		1000		0	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
WP1	0,00		0		1000		0	
WP1-Coordination	0,00		0		1000	1 Final meeting	0	
P08-VRI	0,00		5000		2500		0	
WP1	0,00		5000		2500		0	
WP1-Coordination	0,00		5000	CFS costs	2500	1 SSB meeting - 1 Stakeholder conference meeting - 1 Final meeting	0	
P09-BfR	0,00		15000		7000		60000	
WP1	0,00		15000		7000		0	
WP1-Coordination	0,00		15000	CFS costs	7000	1 SSB meeting - 1 Stakeholder conference meeting - 1 Final meeting	0	
WP4	0,00		0		0		0	
JIP06-COVID19-COVRIN	0,00		0		0		0	
WP5	0,00		0		0		60000	
WP5-Science to Policy translation	0,00		0		0		60000	Stakeholder conference
P10-FLI	0,00		18843		2700		0	
WP1	0,00		13000		2000		0	
WP1-Coordination	0,00		13000	CFS costs	2000	1 SSB meeting - 1 Stakeholder conference	0	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
						meeting - 1 Final meeting		
WP4	0,00		5843		700		0	
JIP06-COVID19-COVRIN	0,00		5843	FLI consumables	700	FLI Interlaboratory exchange	0	
P11-RKI	0,00		8000		2500		0	
WP1	0,00		8000		2500		0	
WP1-Coordination	0,00		8000	CFS costs	2500	1 SSB meeting - 1 Stakeholder conference meeting - 1 Final meeting	0	
P12-DTU	0,00		2500		4000		0	
WP1	0,00		2500		4000		0	
WP1-Coordination	0,00		2500	CFS costs	4000	1 SSB meeting - 1 Stakeholder conference meeting - 1 Final meeting	0	
P13-SSI	0,00		3000		8000		0	
WP1	0,00		0		8000		0	
WP1-Coordination	0,00		0		8000	1 SSB meeting - 1 Stakeholder conference meeting - 1 Final meeting	0	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
WP3	0,00		0		0		0	
WP3-JRPs management	0,00		0		0		0	
WP5	0,00		3000		0		0	
WP5-Science to Policy translation	0,00		3000	Publication fee	0		0	
P14-UT	0,00		7000		2500		0	
WP1	0,00		7000		2500		0	
WP1-Coordination	0,00		7000	CFS costs	2500	1 SSB meeting - 1 Stakeholder conference meeting - 1 Final meeting	0	
P15-VFL	0,00		0		2500		0	
WP1	0,00		0		2500		0	
WP1-Coordination	0,00		0		2500	1 SSB meeting - 1 Stakeholder conference meeting - 1 Final meeting	0	
P16-INIA	0,00		500		4100		0	
WP1	0,00		500		2500		0	
WP1-Coordination	0,00		500	CFS costs	2500	1 SSB meeting - 1 Stakeholder conference meeting - 1 Final meeting	0	
WP4	0,00		0		1600		0	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JIP06-COVID19-COVRIN	0,00		0		1600	Final meeting COVRIN 2023	0	
P17-UCM	0,00		5204		7000		0	
WP1	0,00		5000		6000		0	
WP1-Coordination	0,00		5000	CFS costs	6000	1 SSB meeting - 1 Stakeholder conference meeting - 1 Final meeting	0	
WP2	0,00		0		1000		0	
WP2-SRA	0,00		0		1000	Various meetings	0	
WP4	0,00		204		0		0	
JIP06-COVID19-COVRIN	0,00		204	Laboratoyr consumables	0		0	
P18-MVNA	0,00		0		500		0	
WP1	0,00		0		500		0	
WP1-Coordination	0,00		0		500	1 SSB meeting - 1 Stakeholder conference meeting - 1 Final meeting	0	
P19-INRAE	0,00		0		3000		0	
WP1	0,00		0		3000		0	
WP1-Coordination	0,00		0		3000	1 SSB meeting - 1 Stakeholder conference	0	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
						meeting - 1 Final meeting		
P20-IP	0,00		3400		3500		0	
WP1	0,00		3400		3500		0	
WP1-Coordination	0,00		3400	CFS costs	3500	1 SSB meeting - 1 Stakeholder conference meeting - 1 Final meeting	0	
P21-APHA	0,00		17208		4500		0	
WP1	0,00		15000		4500		0	
WP1-Coordination	0,00		15000	CFS costs	4500	1 SSB meeting - 1 Stakeholder conference meeting - 1 Final meeting	0	
WP4	0,00		2208		0		0	
JIP06-COVID19-COVRIN	0,00		2208	Consumables - Microchips - Ferret purchase - Ferret transport - Ferret B&B with staff component removed	0		0	
P22-PHE	0,00		0		1000		0	
WP1	0,00		0		1000		0	
WP1-Coordination	0,00		0		1000	1 Final meeting	0	
P23-UoS	0,00		10330		16000		0	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
WP1	0,00		9230		13000		0	
WP1-Coordination	0,00		9230	CFS costs - Website operating cost - hosting costs	13000	1 SSB meeting - 1 Stakeholder conference meeting - 1 Final meeting	0	
WP4	0,00		1100		0		0	
JIP06-COVID19-COVRIN	0,00		1100	Consumables - Storage access	0		0	
WP6	0,00		0		3000		0	
WP6-T&E management	0,00		0		3000	SSB meeting - Final meeting	0	
P24-NNK	0,00		0		1000		0	
WP1	0,00		0		1000		0	
WP1-Coordination	0,00		0		1000	1 Final meeting	0	
P25-NUIG	0,00		3000		3000		0	
WP1	0,00		3000		3000		0	
WP1-Coordination	0,00		3000	CFS costs	3000	1 SSB meeting - 1 Stakeholder conference meeting - 1 Final meeting	0	
P26-TEAGASC	0,00		0		2500		0	
WP1	0,00		0		2500		0	
WP1-Coordination	0,00		0		2500	1 SSB meeting - 1 Stakeholder conference	0	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
						meeting - 1 Final meeting		
P27-ISS	0,00		25000		6260		0	
WP1	0,00		25000		5000		0	
WP1-Coordination	0,00		25000	CFS costs	5000	1 SSB meeting - 1 Stakeholder conference meeting - 1 Final meeting	0	
WP4	0,00		0		1260		0	
JIP06-COVID19-COVRIN	0,00		0		1260	Final meeting COVRIN 2023	0	
WP7	0,00		0		1000		0	
WP7-Sustainability	0,00		0		0		0	
P28-IZS AM	0,00		8000		2000		0	
WP1	0,00		8000		2000		0	
WP1-Coordination	0,00		8000	CFS costs	2000	1 SSB meeting - 1 Stakeholder conference meeting - 1 Final meeting	0	
WP4	0,00		0		0		0	
JIP06-COVID19-COVRIN	0,00		0		0		0	
P29-IZS LER	0,00		6950		2000		0	
WP1	0,00		5000		2000		0	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
WP1-Coordination	0,00		5000	CFS costs	2000	1 SSB meeting - 1 Stakeholder conference meeting - 1 Final meeting	0	
WP4	0,00		1950		0		0	
JIP06-COVID19-COVRIN	0,00		1950	serological kits, plastics and reagent for serology - reagents for molecular biology - reagents and plastics for virus isolation	0		0	
P30-RIVM	0,00		8000		6500		0	
WP1	0,00		8000		5500		0	
WP1-Coordination	0,00		8000	CFS costs	5500	1 SSB meeting - 1 Stakeholder conference meeting - 1 Final meeting	0	
WP2	0,00		0		1000		0	
WP2-SRA	0,00		0		1000	Various meetings	0	
WP4	0,00		0		0		0	
JIP06-COVID19-COVRIN	0,00		0		0		0	
P31-WbvR	0,00		7084		5300		2000	
WP1	0,00		4800		5000		0	
WP1-Coordination	0,00		4800	CFS costs	5000	1 SSB meeting - 1 Stakeholder	0	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
						conference meeting - 1 Final meeting		
WP4	0,00		2284		0		2000	
JIP06-COVID19-COVRIN	0,00		2284	Consumables and disposables	0		2000	Kick-off meeting
WP6	0,00		0		300		0	
WP6-T&E management	0,00		0		300	1 SSB meeting - 1 Stakeholder conference meeting - 1 Final meeting	0	
P32-FHI	0,00		10000		1500		0	
WP1	0,00		10000		1500		0	
WP1-Coordination	0,00		10000	CFS costs	1500	1 SSB meeting - 1 Stakeholder conference meeting - 1 Final meeting	0	
P33-NVI	0,00		13132		2000		0	
WP1	0,00		13000		2000		0	
WP1-Coordination	0,00		13000	CFS costs	2000	1 SSB meeting - 1 Stakeholder conference meeting - 1 Final meeting	0	
WP4	0,00		132		0		0	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
WP4-JIPs management					0			
JIP06-COVID19-COVRIN	0,00		132	RNASeq costs	0		0	
P34-PIWET	0		10936		2500		0	
WP1	0,00		4500		2500		0	
WP1-Coordination	0,00		4500	CFS costs	2500	1 SSB meeting - 1 Stakeholder conference meeting - 1 Final meeting	0	
WP4	0,00		6436		0		0	
JIP06-COVID19-COVRIN	0,00		6436	Test reagents - Disposables - services i.e. sampling, DNA sequencing, shipment	0		0	
P35-INIAV	0		6750		2500		0	
WP1	0,00		6000		2500		0	
WP1-Coordination	0,00		6000	CFS costs	2500	1 SSB meeting - 1 Stakeholder conference meeting - 1 Final meeting	0	
WP4	0,00		750		0		0	
JIP06-COVID19-COVRIN	0,00		750	Project Management and communication expenses - Expenses involved in phylodynamic studies	0		0	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
P36-INSA	0		12300		4000		0	
WP1	0,00		12300		4000		0	
WP1-Coordination	0,00		12300	CFS costs	4000	1 SSB meeting - 1 Stakeholder conference meeting - 1 Final meeting	0	
WP4	0,00		0		0		0	
WP4-JIPs management	0,00		0		0		0	
JIP06-COVID19-COVRIN	0,00		0		0		0	
P37-IISPV	0		0		1000		0	
WP1	0,00		0		1000		0	
WP1-Coordination	0,00		0		1000	1 Final meeting	0	
P39-SLV	0,00		0		2500		0	
WP1	0,00		0		2500		0	
WP1-Coordination	0,00		0		2500	1 SSB meeting - 1 Stakeholder conference meeting - 1 Final meeting	0	
P40-FoHM	0,00		20000		3000		0	
WP1	0,00		20000		3000		0	
WP1-Coordination	0,00		20000	CFS costs	3000	1 SSB meeting - 1 Stakeholder conference meeting - 1 Final meeting	0	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
P41-SVA	0,00		11812		10000		0	
WP1	0,00		10000		10000		0	
WP1-Coordination	0,00		10000	CFS costs	10000	1 SSB meeting - 1 Stakeholder conference meeting - 1 Final meeting	0	
WP4	0,00		1812		0		0	
WP4-JIPs management	0,00		0		0		0	
JIP06-COVID19-COVRIN	0,00		1812	NGS-investigations - Screening of Domestic and companion animals for CoV - Screening of wild life for CoV - Patological investigations - Risk assessment and surveillance (sampling)	0		0	
WP7	0,00		0		1000		0	
WP7-Sustainability	0,00		0		0		0	
P42-NMVRVI	0,00		0		2500		0	
WP1	0,00		0		2500		0	
WP1-Coordination	0,00		0		2500	1 SSB meeting - 1 Stakeholder conference	0	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
						meeting - 1 Final meeting		
P43-ISCIH	0,00		0		2000		0	
WP1	0,00		0		2000		0	
WP1-Coordination	0,00		0		2000	1 SSB meeting - 1 Stakeholder conference meeting - 1 Final meeting	0	
P44-BIOR	0,00		0		3350		0	
WP1	0,00		0		2500		0	
WP1-Coordination	0,00		0		2500	1 SSB meeting - 1 Stakeholder conference meeting - 1 Final meeting	0	
WP4	0,00		0		850		0	
JIP06-COVID19-COVRIN	0,00		0		850	Final meeting COVRIN 2023	0	
P45-RUOKA	0,00		0		2500		0	
WP1	0,00		0		2500		0	
WP1-Coordination	0,00		0		2500	1 SSB meeting - 1 Stakeholder conference meeting - 1 Final meeting	0	
P46-THL	0,00		0		2500		0	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
WP1	0,00		0		2500		0	
WP1-Coordination	0,00		0		2500	1 SSB meeting - 1 Stakeholder conference meeting - 1 Final meeting	0	
P47-NEBIH	0,00		0		2500		0	
WP1	0,00		0		2500		0	
WP1-Coordination	0,00		0		2500	1 SSB meeting - 1 Stakeholder conference meeting - 1 Final meeting	0	
TOTAL	0,00		294641		166510		109868,3	